

Report 2015

Trends and Sources of Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and Feedingstuffs

Austria

Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2015

1. List of Contents

1.	LIST OF CONTENTS	- 4 -
2.	INFORMATION ON THE REPORTING AND MONITORING SYSTEM	- 6 -
3.	ANIMAL POPULATIONS	- 13 -
3.1.	Information on susceptible animal population	- 13 -
4.	INFORMATION ON SPECIFIC ZOOSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS	- 16 -
4.1.	SALMONELLOSIS	- 18 -
4.1.1.	General evaluation	- 18 -
4.1.2.	Salmonellosis in humans	- 18 -
4.1.3.	<i>Salmonella</i> spp. in foodstuffs	- 22 -
4.1.4.	<i>Salmonella</i> spp. in animals	- 40 -
4.1.5.	<i>Salmonella</i> spp. in feeding stuff	- 56 -
4.1.6.	<i>Salmonella</i> serovars and phage type distribution	- 62 -
4.1.7.	Antimicrobial resistance in <i>Salmonella</i> spp. isolates	- 67 -
4.2.	CAMPYLOBACTERIOSIS	- 83 -
4.2.1.	General evaluation	- 83 -
4.2.2.	Campylobacteriosis in humans	- 84 -
4.2.3.	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in foodstuffs	- 86 -
4.2.4.	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in animals	- 91 -
4.2.5.	Antimicrobial resistance in <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	- 91 -
4.3.	LISTERIOSIS	- 108 -
4.3.1.	General evaluation	- 108 -
4.3.2.	Listeriosis in humans	- 108 -
4.3.3.	<i>Listeria</i> spp. in foodstuffs	- 111 -
4.4.	VEROTOXIC <i>ESCHERICHIA COLI</i>	- 124 -
4.4.1.	General evaluation	- 124 -
4.4.2.	Verocytotoxic <i>Escherichia coli</i> in humans	- 124 -
4.4.3.	Pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> in foodstuffs	- 126 -
4.4.4.	Pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> in animals	- 139 -
4.5.	TUBERCULOSIS	- 140 -
4.5.1.	General evaluation	- 140 -
4.5.2.	Tuberculosis in humans	- 140 -
4.5.3.	<i>Mycobacterium</i> spp. in animals	- 142 -
4.6.	BRUCELLOSIS	- 148 -
4.6.1.	General evaluation of the national situation	- 148 -
4.6.2.	Brucellosis in humans	- 148 -
4.6.3.	<i>Brucella</i> in foodstuffs	- 150 -
4.6.4.	<i>Brucella</i> spp. in animals	- 150 -
4.7.	YERSINIOSIS	- 158 -
4.7.1.	General evaluation	- 158 -
4.7.2.	Yersiniosis in humans	- 158 -
4.7.3.	<i>Yersinia</i> in foodstuffs	- 160 -
4.7.4.	<i>Yersinia</i> spp. in animals	- 161 -

4.8. TRICHINELLOSIS	- 162 -
4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation	- 162 -
4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans	- 162 -
4.8.3. <i>Trichinella</i> spp. in animals	- 163 -
4.9. ECHINOCOCCOSIS	- 168 -
4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation	- 168 -
4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans	- 168 -
4.9.3. <i>Echinococcus</i> spp. in animals	- 170 -
4.10. TOXOPLASMOSIS	- 172 -
4.10.1. General evaluation	- 172 -
4.10.2. <i>Toxoplasma</i> in humans	- 172 -
4.10.3. <i>Toxoplasma</i> in animals	- 173 -
4.11. RABIES	- 175 -
4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation	- 175 -
4.11.2. Rabies in humans	- 175 -
4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals	- 176 -
4.12. Q-FEVER	- 179 -
4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation	- 179 -
4.12.2. Q-fever in humans	- 179 -
4.12.3. <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in animals	- 179 -
5. INFORMATION ON SPECIFIC INDICATORS OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE	- 181 -
5.1. E. COLI INDICATORS	- 181 -
5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation	- 181 -
5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance of <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolates from animals	- 182 -
5.1.3. Antimicrobial resistance of <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolates from food	- 187 -
5.2. ENTEROCOCCUS INDICATORS	- 204 -
5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation	- 204 -
6. FOOD-BORNE OUTBREAKS	- 205 -
7. INFORMATION ON SPECIFIC MICROBIOLOGICAL AGENTS	- 211 -
7.1. STAPHYLOCOCCAL ENTEROTOXINS	- 211 -
7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation	- 211 -
7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff	- 212 -
7.2. CRONOBACTER SAKAZAKII	- 213 -
7.2.1. <i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i> in foodstuff	- 213 -
7.3. HISTAMINE	- 214 -
7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation	- 214 -
7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff	- 214 -
8. INDEX OF TABLES	217

2. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2015

This report was prepared by the Departments for Statistics and Data Management of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Authorities		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Water management	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	Nine provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporters); analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., and <i>E. coli</i> ; mapping of food and feed data; creation of xml-files, upload of data to DCF
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Infectious Epidemiology Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning notifiable zoonotic diseases in humans and food borne outbreaks
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Centre for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Laboratory for antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Toxoplasmoselabor und Nachsorgeambulanz Toxoplasmose, Diagnostik in der Schwangerschaft und kindliches Follow-up, The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, Klinische Abteilung für Neonatologie, pädiatrische Intensivmedizin und Neuropädiatrie, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Medical University of Vienna	Data concerning toxoplasmosis in humans

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in food
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in food

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning monitoring programmes in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of <i>E. coli</i> from animals
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing

PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2015. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual European Union Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i>
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
BMGF	Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
PHD	Poultry Health Data
RDNC	reaction pattern does not conform to the phage scheme
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verocytotoxin producing <i>E. coli</i>

3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria. Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings, flocks and animals is based on the Poultry Health Data. All holdings, flocks and animals are part of the *Salmonella* control program. In Austria there are also holdings with a small number of animals that are not covered by the *Salmonella* control program and these numbers of holdings, flocks and animals are not presented in the following table.

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in main poultry-slaughterhouses performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from Poultry Health Data.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 163/2012 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen).

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.18 % of all pigs are kept in 82.11 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 72.71 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74.89 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 69.78 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 77.90 % of the goats are kept there.

Solipeds: 67.46 % of the soliped holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 70.68 % of the solipeds are kept there.

Deer: 89.33 % of the deer holdings are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria; 89.91% of the deer are kept there.

Cattle: 74.13 % of the cattle holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and Tirol; 77.50% of the cattle are kept there.

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of animals, herds, holdings and slaughtered animals, 2015

	Animals species	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	holding	63,476	Veterinary Information System
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	animal	1,965,618	Veterinary Information System
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	slaughter animal (heads)	631,420	incl. young cattle (9-12m) but without calves
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	animal	626,091	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	slaughter animal (heads)	63,754	calves only, Data established by Statistics Austria
in total	Pigs	holding	34,977	Veterinary Information System
in total	Pigs	animal	3,063,906	Veterinary Information System
in total	Pigs	slaughter animal (heads)	5,414,234	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	holding	6,108	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	animal	253,352	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	slaughter animal (heads)	90,752	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - fattening pigs	holding	26,583	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - fattening pigs	animal	1,175,912	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Pigs - fattening pigs	slaughter animal (heads)	5,323,482	Data established by Statistics Austria
in total	Sheep	holding	17,901	Veterinary Information System
in total	Sheep	animal	445,421	Veterinary Information System
in total	Sheep	slaughter animal (heads)	264,304	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	holding	16,749	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	animal	260,028	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	63,357	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	holding	14,074	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	animal	185,393	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	slaughter animal (heads)	200,947	Data established by Statistics Austria
in total	Goats	holding	11,373	Veterinary Information System
in total	Goats	animal	103,850	Veterinary Information System
in total	Goats	slaughter animal (heads)	49,981	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals over 1 year	holding	11,059	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals over 1 year	animal	71,830	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals over 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	12,711	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals under 1 year	holding	5,358	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals under 1 year	animal	32,020	Data established by Statistics Austria
	Goats - animals under 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	37,270	Data established by Statistics Austria
in total	Solipeds, domestic	holding	18,584	Veterinary Information System
in total	Solipeds, domestic	animal	89,836	Veterinary Information System
in total	Solipeds, domestic	slaughter animal (heads)	783	Data established by Statistics Austria

Animal Populations

Animals species		Unit	Number	comments
in total	Deer - farmed	holding	1,958	Veterinary Information System
in total	Deer - farmed	animal	44,831	Veterinary Information System
in total	Deer - farmed	slaughter animal (heads)		unknown
in total	Wild boars - farmed	holding	18	Veterinary Information System
in total	Wild boars - farmed	animal	200	Veterinary Information System
in total	Wild boars - farmed	slaughter animal (heads)		unknown
in total	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)	slaughter animal (heads)	80,722,620	hens for roasting, baking and for soup; data established by Statistics Austria
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	holding	56	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	animal	946,063	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	herd/flock	122	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	holding	14	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	animal	147,584	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	herd/flock	13	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers	holding	496	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers	animal	64,111,984	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers	herd/flock	4,146	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - laying hens	holding	1,081	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - laying hens	animal	9,504,324	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - laying hens	herd/flock	2,768	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	holding	56	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	animal	946,063	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	herd/flock	122	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	holding	14	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	animal	147,584	Poultry Health Data
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	herd/flock	13	Poultry Health Data
in total	Turkeys	holding	135	Poultry Health Data
in total	Turkeys	animal	1,884,190	Poultry Health Data
in total	Turkeys	herd/flock	365	Poultry Health Data
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	holding	135	Poultry Health Data
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	animal	1,884,190	Poultry Health Data
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	herd/flock	365	Poultry Health Data

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the MOH. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). Also the laboratories enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMGF-homepage:

http://www.BMGF.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Epidemiologie/Jahresstatistiken_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_seit_dem_Jahr_2000).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers

are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2015, the number of notified salmonellosis cases (1,514) decreased compared to 2014 by 6% but did not reach the lowest level from 2013 (1,433 cases) and remained the second highest reported food-borne pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The *Salmonella*-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, and increased in 2012 to 9.3 % and in 2013 to 10 % and in 2014 to 11.5 % and to 15% in 2015 due to the fact that *S. Infantis* prevalence is still high in poultry meat (7 %). The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with *Salmonella* is presumably the main cause of human infection (*S. Enteritidis*). The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 1,514 cases. This number shows a decrease compared to the previous year but still remained higher than in 2013 (n = 1,433). As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), *Salmonella* is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined within the last years. Different foodstuffs (e.g. poultry meat, eggs, or mixed foodstuffs) may pose a certain risk therefore kitchen hygiene is of utmost importance.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of *Salmonella* in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain and update the target serovars in the different poultry populations, e.g. *S. Infantis* in broiler flocks or *S. Stanley* in turkey flocks.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, who are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea

- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Salmonella* (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* (NRC-*Salmonella*) all isolates are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with *Salmonella* increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of *Salmonella* illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* cases has decreased by 82 % (2002: 8,403 cases, 2015: 1,514 notified cases).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, the number of human laboratory confirmed cases of salmonellosis notified to EMS decreased compared to 2014 but the number was higher than in 2013 (1,433 cases). The proportion of *S. Enteritidis* isolates out of all *Salmonella* cases decreased in 2013 to 43.3 % (2014: 49.3%; 2013: 42.4 %). The most frequently identified Enteritidis phage types in 2015 were: PT 8 (297 cases), PT 21 (64 cases), and PT 4 (43 cases). The proportion of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported increased slightly to 12.7 % (2014: 12.2%, 2013: 7.2 %; 2012: 13.9 %). Most frequent definitive type was DT 120 (42 cases). 42 isolates of monophasic *S. group B* (1,4,[5],12:i:-) were found in humans (2014: 63 cases, 2013: 68 cases).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2015, the number of notified human laboratory confirmed cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria on monthly and yearly basis. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1,514	17.65	1,126	311	77
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	656	7,65	451	164	41
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	192	2,24	159	25	8
<i>S. Stanley</i>	166	1,94	154	10	2
<i>S. Infantis</i>	69	0,80	56	6	7
<i>S. Typhimurium, monophasic 1.4.[5].12:l:-</i>	42	0,49	36	6	
<i>S. Paratyphi B var. L(+)</i> tartrate+ (variant Java)	23	0,27	15	8	
<i>S. Group (B) O:4</i>	21	0,24	16	4	1
serotype unknown	21	0,24	17	2	2
<i>S. Coeln</i>	19	0,22	17	2	
<i>S. Thompson</i>	16	0,19	11	5	
<i>S. Agona</i>	13	0,15	6	6	1
<i>S. Newport</i>	13	0,15	6	5	2
<i>S. Virchow</i>	12	0,14	7	4	1
<i>S. Bareilly</i>	11	0,13	9	2	
<i>S. Hadar</i>	11	0,13	3	8	
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	10	0,12	6	3	1
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	10	0,12	9	1	
<i>S. Subspecies II (salamae)</i>	10	0,12	8	2	
<i>S. Derby</i>	8	0,09	7		1
<i>S. Subspecies IIIb (diarizonae)</i>	8	0,09	7	1	
<i>S. Mikawasima</i>	7	0,08	4	3	
<i>S. Stanleyville</i>	7	0,08	4	3	
<i>S. Muenchen</i>	6	0,07	6		
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>	6	0,07	6		
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	5	0,06	3	1	1
<i>S. Group (C1) O:7</i>	5	0,06	5		
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	5	0,06	4	1	
<i>S. Muenster</i>	5	0,06	2	3	
<i>S. Panama</i>	5	0,06	5		
<i>S. Putten</i>	5	0,06	4		1
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	5	0,06	5		
<i>S. Bredeney</i>	4	0,05	1	3	
<i>S. Indiana</i>	4	0,05	4		
<i>S. Kenya</i>	4	0,05	4		
<i>S. Montevideo</i>	4	0,05	1	3	
<i>S. Napoli</i>	4	0,05	3		1
<i>S. Ordonez</i>	4	0,05	3		1
<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	4	0,05	4		
<i>S. Weltevreden</i>	4	0,05	1	3	
<i>S. Abony</i>	3	0,03	1	1	1
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	3	0,03	3		
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	3	0,03	1	2	
<i>S. Haifa</i>	3	0,03		3	
<i>S. Livingstone</i>	3	0,03	2	1	
<i>S. London</i>	3	0,03	1		2
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	3	0,03	3		
<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	3	0,03	3		
<i>S. Stourbridge</i>	3	0,03	3		

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1,514	17.65	1,126	311	77
S. Szentes	3	0,03	2	1	
S. Albany	2	0,02	1	1	
S. Amsterdam	2	0,02	2		
S. Blockley	2	0,02	2		
S. Braenderup	2	0,02		2	
S. Chester	2	0,02	1	1	
S. Heidelberg	2	0,02	1	1	
S. Isangi	2	0,02	2		
S. Kedougou	2	0,02	2		
S. Litchfield	2	0,02	2		
S. Monschau	2	0,02	2		
S. Teitelkebir	2	0,02	2		
S. Veneziana	2	0,02	1	1	
S. Adjame	1	0,01		1	
S. Anatum	1	0,01	1		
S. Bardo	1	0,01		1	
S. Cerro	1	0,01		1	
S. Chomedey	1	0,01		1	
S. Colindale	1	0,01	1		
S. Cullingworth	1	0,01	1		
S. Dakar	1	0,01	1		
S. Eastbourne	1	0,01	1		
S. Essen	1	0,01		1	
S. Galiema	1	0,01		1	
S. Give	1	0,01	1		
S. Goldcoast	1	0,01	1		
S. Group O:3,10 (E1)	1	0,01	1		
S. I (S. enterica subsp. enterica) rough	1	0,01	1		
S. II (S. enterica subsp. salamae	1	0,01	1		
S. IIIb (S. enterica subsp. diarizonae) 38:z52:z53	1	0,01			1
S. Irumu	1	0,01			1
S. Istanbul	1	0,01	1		
S. Johannesburg	1	0,01	1		
S. Kambole	1	0,01		1	
S. Liverpool	1	0,01	1		
S. Manhattan	1	0,01		1	
S. monophasic strain E1-group 3,10:b:-	1	0,01			1
S. Ndolo	1	0,01	1		
S. Oslo	1	0,01		1	
S. Poona	1	0,01		1	
S. Roan	1	0,01	1		
S. S. Chester	1	0,01		1	
S. Salford	1	0,01	1		
S. Strathcona	1	0,01	1		
S. Sundsvall	1	0,01	1		
S. Uganda	1	0,01		1	
S. Umbilo	1	0,01		1	
S. Utah	1	0,01	1		
S. Worthington	1	0,01	1		

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

age groups	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Stanley		S. Infantis		S. Typhimurium, monophasic		other and unknown serotypes	
	all	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
< 1 year	48	27	21	5	9	6	4	1		1	1			14	7
1 to 4 years	199	106	93	49	50	22	17	4	3	5	4	1	4	25	15
5 to 14 years	278	161	117	80	68	20	20	26	9	1	2	5	3	29	15
15 to 24 years	260	147	113	48	51	16	5	42	16	4	6	4	7	33	28
25 to 44 years	291	156	135	53	49	15	15	23	12	15	11	2	3	48	45
45 to 64 years	259	156	103	68	50	18	11	14	6	7	4	2	4	47	28
65 years and older	179	80	99	36	40	9	14	8	2	3	5	2	5	22	33
All age groups	1,514	833	681	339	317	106	86	118	48	36	33	16	26	218	171

Data source: EMS, NRC-S 29.04.2016

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

Month	Salmonellosis	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Stanley	S. Infantis	S. Typhimurium, monophasic	other and unknown serotypes
January	81	45	7	8	1	1	19
February	52	13	7	17	2	1	12
March	73	23	6	7	2	2	33
April	68	28	3	6	4	4	23
May	96	30	7	29	4	3	23
June	135	59	14	14	9	7	32
July	175	77	24	25	10	3	36
August	251	120	34	36	11	3	47
September	220	96	31	11	11	7	64
October	172	91	26	6	6	6	37
November	120	45	24	4	5	5	37
December	71	29	9	3	4		26
Total	1,514	656	192	166	69	42	389

Data source: EMS, NRC-S 29.04.2016

4.1.3. *Salmonella* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are

used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, minced meat, eggs, vegetables, etc.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2002 + Cor.1:2004 + Amd.1:2007. The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exceptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005, as indicated in tables 5-8. All *Salmonella* isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* in Graz and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility according to EUCAST. In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions (e.g. new regulations, new control programs, etc.) taken.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

All *Salmonella* serotypes should be covered by monitoring programs and/or microbiological criteria.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Whenever *Salmonella* is detected the isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored. Investigation into the source of the contamination is initiated if indicated.

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 22.7% (30 out of 132) and in 3.0% of fresh turkey meat samples (2 out of 66). In the remaining fresh meat samples (n=23) from duck meat, geese meat and unspecified poultry meat three *Salmonella* have been detected. Meat preparations, raw but intended to be eaten cooked contained *Salmonella* in 23.46% (CI:16-34%) of broiler meat, whereas 9 of 117 poultry meat preparations (broiler, turkey, unspecified) were tested positive (7.7%; CI:4-14%). All poultry meat products, no matter if cooked or raw, contained *Salmonella* in 4 of 54 samples (7.4%; CI 3-18%).

Segregating the data for processing plant, cutting plant and slaughter house (fresh broiler meat), 7 samples were tested positive for *Salmonella* (39 samples tested). Comparing the prevalence at these sampling stages to the previous year (5% positive, out of 20), this number increased to 17.9% (CI 9-33%). At the processing plant all *Salmonella* found where *S. Infantis*, whereas at the slaughterhouse *S. Montevideo* has been detected.

In total 963 samples of meat, minced meat, meat products and meat preparations (poultry not included) were tested, with 5 positive sample for *Salmonella*.

No *Salmonella* were found in 900 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2007-2014. 2,525 samples of different matrices were tested for *Salmonella*, resulting in two positive findings in the categories other food and frozen, ready-to-eat foods. One sample of liquid egg products contained *S. Enteritidis*, out of 55 samples of egg products Out of the 83 samples from packing centres, processing plants, retail, catering or wholesale one sample was tested positive for *Salmonella* Typhimurium in table eggs at retail.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks. Since January 2012, the Outbreak Detection System (ODS) for the early detection of Salmonellosis has been installed in Austria. Within this tool realtime data on *Salmonella* isolates are utilized to determine a threshold value. If the number of *Salmonella* cases of the current week exceeds this threshold, a signal indicates a possible outbreak. This signal enables an early start of outbreak investigations.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-023-15: *Salmonella* in food – infant formula – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May to June

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Infant formula, containing cereals

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

30 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Campaign A-026-15: *Salmonella* spp. in food – fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – single (food/feed) – at catering – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured (tuna samples in open cans from restaurants and food stalls)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

74 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Histamine.

Campaign A-047-15: *Salmonella* spp. in food – meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked – batch (food/feed) – at catering – monitoring – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Sampling is done because of an *S. Stanley* outbreak. The meat product “Kebap” was suspected to be the source.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September to October

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Kebap

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

15 batches (5 samples with at least 25 g each) were tested for *Salmonella* spp.

11 batches were negative in all 5 samples, but 4 batches were positive at least in one. Two *S. enterica* subsp. *diarizonae*, two *S. Derby*, one *S. Saintpaul*, and four *S. Infantis* have been detected in these four positive batches.

Campaign A-802-15: *Salmonella* spp. in food – Fruits and vegetable – non-pre-cut – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and catering companies by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables (like tomatoes, cucumbers, and berries (like strawberries, raspberries, ...) fresh and frozen

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

75 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* and VTEC.

Campaign A-803-15: *Salmonella* spp. in food – cheeses, spreadable and pig meat products - pâté – at catering and retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and catering companies by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - spreadable, meat from pig - meat products - pâté

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

49 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes* and VTEC.

Table 5 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Agona	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Derby	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. enterica subsp. diarizonae	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. enterica subsp. enterica	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 1	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 6a	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Heidelberg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Kentucky	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Montevideo	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Newport	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Saintpaul	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Stanley	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Thompson	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - 2	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - DT 8	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - RDNC			
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cutting plant		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		29	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		64	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	16	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Slaughterhouse		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		10	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		69	19	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from duck - fresh			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0		
				Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from geese - fresh			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from geese - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

Table 5 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Agona	Salmonella - S. Derby	Salmonella - S. enterica subsp. diarizonae	Salmonella - S. enterica subsp. enterica	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 1	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 6a	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	Salmonella - S. Heidelberg	Salmonella - S. infantis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Montevideo	Salmonella - S. Newport	Salmonella - S. Saintpaul	Salmonella - S. Senftenberg	Salmonella - S. Stanley	Salmonella - S. Thompson	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - 2	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 8	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - RDNC		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		19	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	19	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	69	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)			25 Gram	4	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)			25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - frozen	A-047-15	Catering	EU	batch (food/feed)	25 Gram		8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	batch (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
25 Gram	4				1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	38	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25 Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey - meat preparation		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 6 *Salmonella* spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Oranienburg</i>		
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		6	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		10	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram		6	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		3	0	0	0	0		
					Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		7	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		16	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		1	0	0	0	
					XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	
		Meat from bovine animals - meat products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0
							Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
					Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		5	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0		
					10 Gram		29	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram		7	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		1	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		1	0	0	0					
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	0	0	0			
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		7	0	0	0	0		
					XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		140	2	0	2	
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		6	0	0	0
Meat from horse - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		3	0	0	0	0		
					Cutting plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		3	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		4	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		1	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram		7	0	0	0	0		
					25 Gram		2	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0	0		
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram		1	0	0	0

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Cutting plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	13	0	0	0	0		
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	1	0	0	0	1		
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	34	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	112	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	10	0	0	0	0			
XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0			
Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - pâté	A-803-15	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - meat preparation		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - land mammals - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	24	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	80	1	0	0	1
			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	26	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	39	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0		
	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	1	0	1	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

Table 7 *Salmonella* spp. in milk and dairy products, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	38	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0

Table 7 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - spreadable	A-803-15	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	137	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	240	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	261	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - sour milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0

Table 8 *Salmonella* spp. in other food, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - 62	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 51	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Oranienburg</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 8	
Bakery products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Bakery products - bread		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Bakery products - cakes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Bakery products - pastry		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	149	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Beverages, alcoholic		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Beverages, non-alcoholic - soft drinks		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cereals and meals		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	66	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Chocolate		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Packing centre	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	63	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Coconut - coconut products		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - 62	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 51	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 8	
Crustaceans - prawns		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Crustaceans - shrimps		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Egg products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Egg products - liquid		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Eggs - table eggs		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					600	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		A-026-15 Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Fish - raw		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - smoked		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0				

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - 62	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 51	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 8
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	A-802-15	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits and vegetables - non-pre-cut	A-802-15	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	48	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Honey		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Infant formula		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	A-023-15	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Infant formula - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Juice - fruit juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EU	single (food/feed)		25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Juice - mixed juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Live bivalve molluscs - mussels		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Mushrooms		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - 62	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 51	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 8	
Nuts and nut products		Processing plant	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Nuts and nut products - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Nuts and nut products - roasted		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Nuts and nut products - salted		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
Other food		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	
Other food of non-animal origin		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	265	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)				25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)				25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Processing plant	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	178	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	EU			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	339	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	EU			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - frozen		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	0	1	0
Ready-to-eat salads		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
Sauce and dressings		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - 62	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 51	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 8		
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Seeds, dried		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
EU	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Spices and herbs		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AT	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Spices and herbs - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Sweets		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Vegetables		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Vegetables - products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		

4.1.4. *Salmonella* spp. in animals

A. *Salmonella* in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks for meat production and broiler flocks

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria, no elite and no grandparent flocks. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled. If a parent flock tests positive for other *Salmonella* serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Broiler flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not intended; only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Every flock is tested at day one

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit. 2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at the hatchery and on the farm: at the hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before the birds are moved to the slaughterhouse at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken. 10 % of all flocks produced per year have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No sampling

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings of 1 gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks: Production period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled feces, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Sampling was in accordance with the Annex of Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

See below

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

See below

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

See above

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Vaccination policy - Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Broiler flocks

In the last years, a multi-resistant clone of *S. Infantis* was isolated from broiler flocks and in 2014 this serotype was identified in more than 50 % of all *Salmonella* positive broiler flocks. To control *S. Infantis* but also *Campylobacter* in broiler flock, the application of a competitive exclusion product for poultry (broilact®) was started in 2015. Each positive flock was treated once. The treatment was co-financed by the Poultry Health Service.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Level of biosecurity was increased.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2010.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonosis

See chapter "other preventive measures than vaccination"

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review the target serovars in the different poultry populations

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation: Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding; culling of the infected flock; disposal of the hatched eggs; abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection; if necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies take place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks (flocks positive for *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* are not slaughtered).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in broiler flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

Results of the investigation

Breeding flocks: In 2015, 122 breeding flocks for meat production were kept in 57 holdings in Austria (one holding with both flocks for meat and egg production). *Salmonella* spp. have been detected in 4 flocks, the target serovars were identified in one flock (*S. Typhimurium* DT 2). Austria met the EU-target that has to be calculated for all breeding flocks (meat and egg production line, n = 149 flocks) of max 1% set for 2015 (0.7%).

Broiler flocks: In 2015, 4.146 broiler flocks were grown up in 496 holdings in Austria. In 129 flocks (3.1%) *Salmonella* spp. have been detected but the target serovars were only identified in one flock (0.02%). Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2015. *S. Infantis* was the most common serovar in 84 flocks (65%), followed by *S. Thompson* in 16 flocks (12%), *S. Mbandaka* (8 flocks, 6%) and *S. Senftenberg* (6 flocks, 5%). In one flock two different serovars could be isolated (*S. Infantis* and *S. Thompson*).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Breeding flocks: The number of breeding flocks has increased in Austria since 2005 from 60 flocks to 149 flocks. Based on that numbers, the EU-target can only be met, if maximum one flock is positive for the target serovars. Since the control program in breeding flocks has been running, the annual target of max. 1% was met with exception of 2005 and 2012.

Broiler flocks: In 2009, the first year of the existence of the *Salmonella* control program in broiler the EU-target of max. 1% could not be achieved, but since then the program was successful and the EU-target was met each year. In the last years the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. was between 2.4% and 3.4% and a decreasing tendency can be calculated; the lowest prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks was observed in 2011 (2.4%).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Salmonella* in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks for egg production and flocks of laying hens**Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**

There are only parent flocks in Austria, no elite and no grandparent flocks. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock

is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled. If a parent flock tests positive for other *Salmonella* serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimize biosecurity.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Laying hens flocks

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks sampling two pairs of boot swabs, at least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011. At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Every flock is tested at day one

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit. 2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at the hatchery and on the farm: at the hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Chickens are tested at day one.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times (at day one, week 8 to 12) and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter with two pairs of boot swabs at farm

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

According to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Rearing period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Production period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces in holdings with enriched cages; official controls: additional dust samples and pooled faeces for antimicrobial testing

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings of 1 gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks: Production period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled feces, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled feces samples

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: At slaughter

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

See day-old chicks

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Vaccination policy - Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Stringent biosecurity

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Laying hens flocks

No.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2010.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target Serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation: Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding; culling of the infected flock; disposal of the hatched eggs; abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection; if necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak; EU regulation No 1237/2007 is in force.

Notification system in place

All positive results from laying flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data to the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (BMGF).

Results of the investigation

Breeding flocks: In 2015, 27 breeding flocks for egg production were kept in 15 holdings in Austria (one holding with both flocks for meat and egg production). *Salmonella* spp. have been detected in one flocks, none of the target serovars was identified in the flocks. Austria met the EU-target that has to be calculated for all breeding flocks (meat and egg production line, n = 149 flocks) of max 1% set for 2015 (0.7%).

Laying flocks: In 2015, 2,768 flocks were in production in 1,081 holdings in Austria. In 26 flocks (0.9%) *Salmonella* spp. have been detected, the target serovars in 10 flocks (0.4%), 6-times *S. Typhimurium* and 4-times *S. Enteritidis*. Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2015.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Breeding flocks: The number of breeding flocks has increased in Austria since 2005 from 60 flocks to 149 flocks. Based on that numbers, the EU-target can only be met, if maximum one flock is positive for the target serovars. Since the control program in breeding flocks has been running, the annual target of max. 1% was met with exception of 2005 and 2012.

Laying flocks: Since 2008 an EU-target has been implemented for laying hens. In 2008, the target set for Austria based on the EU-baseline survey was max 8.6%, since then max 2 %. Austria met the EU-target each year with the exception of 2009. The prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. Positive flocks has been successfully reduced from 4.3% in 2007 to 0.9% in 2015.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Salmonella* in other poultry, turkey flocks

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Meat production flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks
no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Rearing period
no legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks
no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Rearing period
no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm
Salmonella spp. isolated from sample material

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

see day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

see day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

no breeding flocks in Austria

Vaccination policy - Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

no breeding flocks in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

no breeding flocks in Austria

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2013.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Meat Production flocks

According to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in turkey broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

Results of the investigation

In 2015, 365 flocks have been fattened in 135 holdings in Austria. *Salmonella* spp. have been detected in 14 flocks (3.8%), the target serovars were identified in 3 flocks (0.8 %) (2-times, one time each *S. Typhimurium* DT2, DT120 and *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic DT193). Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2015.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, Austria again met the EU-target. Since 2010 the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. Has shown a decreasing trend. In 2013 the highest prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. was detected (36 flocks, 10.1%), in 2014 the lowest so far (12 flocks, 3.3%), in 2015 in 14 flocks (3.8%).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2015

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Enteritidis	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT 2	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Mbandaka	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Nyborg	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Senftenberg	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Tennessee	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S.</i> Thompson
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	13	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	27	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock		27	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	61	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	122	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	*	122	4	0	1	1	1	1	1	0

PHD: Poultry Health Data; A = animal sample

* two serovars in one flock (*S.* Mbandaka and *S.* Senftenberg)

Table 10 *Salmonella* spp. in other commercial poultry, 2015

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Agona</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Braenderup</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Coelh</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Corvallis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>diarizonae</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 13a	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 4	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 7	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 8	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Give</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>Salmonella</i> group O:7	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Mbandaka</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Nyborg</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Paratyphi B</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Putten</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Senftenberg</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Stanley</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Tennessee</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Thompson</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 1041	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 120	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 166	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 193	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 2	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - RDNC	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - U	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic - DT 193	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Venezia</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Virchow</i>				
Gallus gallus (fowl), Laying hens																																																		
During rearing period, control and eradication programmes	415	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		415	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0						
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,768	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	1)	2,768	26	10	4	6	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	0	0	0	1	3	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	1	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,768	PHD	Census sampling	Industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		2,556	14	4	1	3	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,768	PHD	Objective sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	2)	1,614	13	6	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,768	PHD	Suspect sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	3)	9	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Gallus gallus (fowl); Broilers																																																		
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	4,146	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	4)	4,146	129	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	84	8	5	2	0	1	0	6	1	1	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Turkeys; Breeding flocks																																																		
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	0	PHD																																																
Turkeys; Fattening flocks																																																		
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	365	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd		365	14	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

PHD: Poultry Health Data

- 1) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT 4 and PT 7) and one flock two different *S. Typhimurium* definitive types (DT 193 and RDNC)
- 2) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT 4 and PT 7)
- 3) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT 4 and PT 7)
- 4) one flock harbouring two serotypes (*S. Infantis* and *S. Thompson*)

4.1.5. *Salmonella* spp. in feeding stuff

Monitoring system – Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Imported feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Imported feed material of animal origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Process control in feed mills

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Compound feedingstuffs

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Compound feedingstuffs

Feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Imported feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Imported feed material of animal origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Process control in feed mills

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Compound feedingstuffs

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Compound feedingstuffs

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Domestic feed material of animal origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Imported feed material of plant origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Imported feed material of animal origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Process control in feed mills
as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Compound feedingstuffs
as above

Control program/mechanisms – The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amendet by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, 3) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007). EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to *Salmonella* monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Control program/mechanisms – Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Control program/mechanisms – Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings – Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Domestic feed material of animal origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Imported feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Imported feed material of animal origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Process control in feed mills

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Compound feedingstuffs

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis - 59 - the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 11 *Salmonella* spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2015

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sampling Origin	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Feed material of land animal origin	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
			EU	25	Gram	6	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 12 *Salmonella* spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2015

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sampling Origin	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Derby	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - RDNC	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Gaminara	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Indiana	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. London	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Reading	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Rissen	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - U	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - 193
Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, broilers - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens final product - pelleted	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	Processing plant	single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	15	5	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	1	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	13	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX	25	Gram	21	5	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1		

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 13 *Salmonella* spp. in other feed matter, 2015

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnit	Gesamt	Gesamt	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Llandoff	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT U291
Feed material of cereal grain origin - barley derived	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - maize derived	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - wheat derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - groundnut derived	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XE	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
EU			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	17	2	0	1	1
EU			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. *Salmonella* serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of *Salmonella* isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the *Salmonella* infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 14 *Salmonella* serovars in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

Serovar	Human, imported	Human, unknown infectious status	Human, autochthonous	Eggs	Meat from broilers	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from duck	Meat from pig	Mixed meat	Other food	Laying hens flock	Broiler flock	Turkey flock	Feed	Pet food
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	311	77	1126	2	37	2	14	2	1	3	2	28	130	15	2	12
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	164	41	451	1	3						1	5	1			1
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	25	8	159	1			1	2				7		2	1	1
<i>S. Stanley</i>	10	2	154		1								1	3		
<i>S. Infantis</i>	6	7	56		24		5			2		1	84	2		2
<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic	6		36											2		1
<i>S. Coeln</i>	2		17										1			
serotype unknown	2	2	17													
<i>S. Group (B) O:4</i>	4	1	16													
<i>S. Paratyphi B</i> var. L(+) tartrate+ (variant Java)	8		15									1				
<i>S. Thompson</i>	5		11				1					3	16			
<i>S. Bareilly</i>	2		9													
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	1		9													
<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>salamae</i>	2		9													
<i>S. Derby</i>		1	7			1	1									1
<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>diarizonae</i>	1	1	7				1					1				
<i>S. Virchow</i>	4	1	7									1				
<i>S. Agona</i>	6	1	6		1		2					1				
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	3	1	6				1									
<i>S. Muenchen</i>			6													
<i>S. Newport</i>	5	2	6			1										
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>			6						1	1	1					
<i>S. Group (C1) O:7</i>			5										3			
<i>S. Panama</i>			5													
<i>S. Tennessee</i>			5										1			
<i>S. Indiana</i>			4													1
<i>S. Kenya</i>			4													
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	1		4									3	8	3		
<i>S. Mikawasima</i>	3		4													
<i>S. Putten</i>		1	4										1			

Serovar	Human, imported	Human, unknown infectious status	Human, autochthonous	Eggs	Meat from broilers	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from duck	Meat from pig	Mixed meat	Other food	Laying hens flock	Broiler flock	Turkey flock	Feed	Pet food
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	311	77	1126	2	37	2	14	2	1	3	2	28	130	15	2	12
S. Senftenberg			4		1							1	6	2		
S. Stanleyville	3		4													
S. Bovismorbificans	1	1	3													
S. Brandenburg			3													
S. Hadar	8		3													
S. Napoli		1	3													
S. Ordonez		1	3													
S. Saintpaul			3				2								1	
S. Schwarzengrund			3													
S. Stourbridge			3													
S. Amsterdam			2													
S. Blockley			2													
S. Isangi			2													
S. Kedougou			2													
S. Litchfield			2													
S. Livingstone	1		2													
S. Monschau			2													
S. Muenster	3		2													
S. Szentcs	1		2													
S. Teitelkebir			2													
S. Abony	1	1	1													
S. Albany	1		1													
S. Anatum			1													
S. Bredeney	3		1													
S. Chester	1		1													
S. Colindale			1													
S. Corvallis	2		1													
S. Cullingworth			1													
S. Dakar			1													
S. Eastbourne			1													
S. Give			1											1		
S. Goldcoast			1													
S. Group O:3,10 (E1)			1													
S. Heidelberg	1		1		1											
S. I (<i>Salmonella</i> enterica subsp. enterica) rough			1													
S. Istanbul			1													
S. Johannesburg			1													
S. Liverpool			1													
S. London		2	1													2
S. Montevideo	3		1		5							2	5			

Serovar	Human, imported	Human, unknown infectious status	Human, autochthonous	Eggs	Meat from broilers	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from duck	Meat from pig	Mixed meat	Other food	Laying hens flock	Broiler flock	Turkey flock	Feed	Pet food
Salmonella spp.	311	77	1126	2	37	2	14	2	1	3	2	28	130	15	2	12
S. Ndolo			1													
S. Roan			1													
S. Salford			1													
S. Strathcona			1													
S. Sundsvall			1													
S. Utah			1													
S. Veneziana	1		1									1				
S. Weltevreden	3		1													
S. Worthington			1													
S. Adjame	1															
S. Bardo	1															
S. Braenderup	2											1				
S. Cerro	1															
S. Chomedey	1															
S. enterica subsp. enterica					1											
S. Essen	1															
S. Galiema	1															
S. Gaminara																1
S. Haifa	3															
S. Irumu		1														
S. Kambole	1															
S. Llandoff																1
S. Manhattan	1															
S. monophasic strain E1-group 3,10:b:-		1														
S. Oslo	1															
S. Poona	1															
S. Reading																1
S. Rissen																1
S. Uganda	1															
S. Umbilo	1															
S. Chester	1															
S. Nyborg													2			

Table 15 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

Phage type	Human, imported	Human, unknown infectious status	Human, autochthonous	Eggs	Meat from broilers	Other food	Laying hens flock	Broiler flock	Pet food
S. Enteritidis	164	41	451	1	3	1	5	1	1
PT 8	52	17	228				2		
PT 21	23	7	34		1				
PT 4	4	5	34				1	1	
PT 5	3		18						
PT 2	2	3	17						
PT 6c	2		17						
PT 14b	8	6	15						
PT 13a	18	1	14						
RDNC	4		10						1
PT 29	8	1	10						
PT 1	16		8		1				
PT 4b			8						
PT 11			6						
PT 21c	4		6						
PT 6a	4		5		1				
PT untypable	1	1	5						
PT 1b	1		5						
PT not typed	1		4						
PT 6	2		3						
PT 12	1		1						
PT 14c			1						
PT 15a	4		1						
PT 9			1						
PT 51						1			
PT 35	1								
PT 56	1								
PT 59	1								
PT 7	1						2		
PT 9a	2								
PT 62				1					

Table 16 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

Definitive type	Human, imported	Human, unknown infectious status	Human, autochthonous	Eggs	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from duck	Laying hens flock	turkey flock	Feed	Pet food
S. Typhimurium	25	8	159	1	1	2	7	2	1	1
DT 120	3		39				1	1		
RDNC	7	4	22		1		2			
DT 1	2		20							
DT 104			19							
DT not typed	1		9							
DT 193	4		8				1			
DT U291	1		6						1	
DT 8		2	5	1	1					
DT 12	1		5							
DT 2		1	4			1		1		
DT 85			3							
DT U302			2							
DT U311	1		2							
DT 10			2							
DT 39			2							
DT 41	1		2							
DT 46			2							
DT U277			1							
DT untypable			1							
DT 110			1							
DT 126a			1							
DT 177			1							
DT 46a			1							
DT 74			1							
DT U284		1								
DT U313	1									
DT 104l							1			
DT 116	2									
DT 166							1			
DT 66a	1									
DT U							1			1

Table 17 S. Typhimurium, monophasic, definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015

definitive type	Human, imported	Human, autochthonous	turkey flock	Pet food
S. Typhimurium, monophasic	6	36	2	1
DT 193	5	33	2	1
DT U311		2		
DT untypable	1	1		

Data source: EMS/NRC-S as of April 29, 2016

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2015 all 1,630 isolates from humans (primary, secondary isolates, from infected person without clinical signs) were tested in the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* for their antimicrobial susceptibility using the diffusion test – or for certain isolates of special interest the ϵ -test – and applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints or if not available those from CLSI. To identify low-level resistance to ciprofloxacin, pefloxacin was tested; in suspicion of high-level resistance to ciprofloxacin the ϵ -test was performed.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Resistance rates increased in the last years. In 2015, resistance rates to certain antimicrobials (ampicillin, sulfonamides, tetracycline) were above 10%, or above 20% (quinolones). The reason for the increase in resistance rates is due to the higher incidence of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, and *S. Kentucky* strains.

In 2015, 7 isolates showed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines, but no resistance to meropenem could be found.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the target serovars in poultry and add new serovars of importance, e.g. those with (multi)resistant phenotypes

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRC-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and poultry flocks

Description of sampling designs

All poultry flocks were subjected to the the national control program, established in accordance with Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (see chapter *Salmonella* in animals). All *Salmonella* isolated from poultry flocks were typed and susceptibility tested using the disk diffusion test in the NRC-S.

C. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. from carcasses of pigs sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Description of sampling designs

All *Salmonella* from pig slaughterhouses in accordance with point 2.1.4 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 were sent to the NRC-S for typing and for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of pigs are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of pigs are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Carcasses of pigs are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Carcasses after dressing but before chilling were sampled.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Carcasses after dressing but before chilling were sampled.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. According to Food Safety and Consumer Protection Law (Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz – LMSVG), Articles 38 (1) Z 6 (duties of the business operator) und § 74 (duties of the analyzing laboratories) all *Salmonella* isolated must be sent to the NRC-*Salmonella*.

According to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU all unique strains isolated in the course of the control programm (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

NRC-*Salmonella*

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animals.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1). In case of resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines or meropenem the testing with panel 2 (Table 4) was performed.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The samples for testing and verification of compliance are performed by the industry in accordance with point 2.1.4 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

In 2015, in pig abattoirs *Salmonella* were not detected in course of the process controls.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Prevalence of *Salmonella* in Austria's pig production is very low (see results from the two baseline surveys in pigs)

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Due to the results, the relevance of Austrian pig meat as vehicle for *Salmonella* infections seem to be very low.

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRC-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2015

antimicrobial	ECOFF	Range tested		zone diameter	
	concentration (µg/ml)			(mm)	
	wild type <=	lowest	highest	resistant <=	
panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,5	32	13
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128	16
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16	15
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,5	0,25	4	16
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,5	8	18
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0,06	0,016	8	23
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,25	8	14
	macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64	-
	penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64	13
	polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16	-
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128	13
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	256	8	1024	12
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64	11
	trimethoprim	2	0,25	32	14
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0,06	0,016	2	21
	carbapenems - imipenem	1	0,12	16	15
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16	15
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0,12	0,06	32	20
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,5	0,25	64	16
	cephalosporines - cefoxitin	8	0,5	64	18
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,25	128	18
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	*	0,06	64	***
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	**	0,12	128	****
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0,5	128	-

presumptive ESBL: *CTX/CTXCL \geq 8 **CAZ/CAZCL \geq 8 *** \emptyset CTXCL at least 5mm $>$ \emptyset CTX **** \emptyset CAZCL at least 5mm $>$ \emptyset CAZ

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or $>$ 4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1630	1,2	20	141	0,0	0	29	24,1	7	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	3,4	1	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1630	2,1	35	141	1,4	2	29	3,4	1	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	1630	0,0	0	141	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1630	0,4	7	141	0,7	1	29	0,0	0	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1630	0,4	6	141	0,7	1	29	0,0	0	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1630	22,3	364	141	86,5	122	29	58,6	17	77	61,0	47	21	9,5	2	29	58,6	17	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1630	0,3	5	141	2,1	3	29	3,4	1	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	1630	13,4	218	141	8,5	12	29	37,9	11	77	3,9	3	21	0,0	0	29	13,8	4	
polymyxins - colistin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1630	21,9	357	141	86,5	122	29	58,6	17	77	61,0	47	21	9,5	2	29	58,6	17	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1630	15,5	252	141	75,2	106	29	41,4	12	77	58,4	45	21	14,3	3	29	17,2	5	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1630	15,6	255	141	75,2	106	29	51,7	15	77	58,4	45	21	14,3	3	29	31,0	9	
trimethoprim	1630	2,1	34	141	5,0	7	29	3,4	1	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates		N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	1630	66,3	1081	141	12,8	18	29	31,0	9	77	35,1	27	21	81,0	17	29	24,1	7	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1630	16,4	268	141	9,2	13	29	17,2	5	77	6,5	5	21	4,8	1	29	51,7	15	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1630	2,8	45	141	1,4	2	29	6,9	2	77	0,0	0	21	9,5	2	29	3,4	1	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1630	9,9	162	141	68,1	96	29	13,8	4	77	57,1	44	21	4,8	1	29	17,2	5	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1630	2,5	40	141	5,0	7	29	3,4	1	77	1,3	1	21	0,0	0	29	3,4	1	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1630	2,1	34	141	3,5	5	29	27,6	8	77	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	29	0,0	0	

Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	698	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	698	0,1	1	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	698	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	698	0,1	1	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	698	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	698	9,2	64	4	75,0	3	3	33,3	1	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	698	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin									0							0	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	698	1,3	9	4	25,0	1	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
polymyxins - colistin																0	0,0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid	698	9,0	63	4	75,0	3	3	33,3	1	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	698	0,6	4	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	698	0,9	6	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
trimethoprim	698	0,1	1	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	0	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	698	89,7	626	4	25,0	1	3	66,7	2	1	100,0	1	4	100,0	4			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	698	9,0	63	4	50,0	2	3	33,3	1	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	698	0,9	6	4	25,0	1	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	698	0,1	1	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	698	0,3	2	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	698	0,0	0	4	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	4	0,0	0			

Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	213	1,4	3	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	213	11,7	25	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	213	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	213	0,9	2	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	213	0,9	2	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	213	5,6	12	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	213	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	213	44,6	95	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	213	5,6	12	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	213	43,7	93	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	5	0,0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	213	40,4	86	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	5	0,0	0	
trimethoprim	213	2,3	5	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	213	50,7	108	1	0,0	0	3	66,7	2				7	85,7	6	5	100,0	5	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	213	4,7	10	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	213	4,7	10	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				7	14,3	1	5	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	213	28,2	60	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	213	7,5	16	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	213	4,2	9	1	100,0	1	3	33,3	1				7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	

Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n																
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	42	2,4	1	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	42	2,4	1	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	42	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	42	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	42	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	42	4,8	2	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	42	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	42	95,2	40	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	3	100,0	3	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	42	4,8	2	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	42	92,9	39	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	3	100,0	3	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	42	92,9	39	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	3	100,0	3	
trimethoprim	42	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n																
fully sensitive	42	0,0	0							1	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	42	2,4	1							1	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	42	11,9	5							1	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	42	81,0	34							1	100,0	1				3	100,0	3	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	42	2,4	1							1	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	42	2,4	1							1	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	

Table 23 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	176	0,6	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	176	96,0	169	1	100,0	1	3	100,0	3	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	13	100,0	13	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	176	5,1	9	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	176	95,5	168	1	100,0	1	3	100,0	3	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	13	100,0	13	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	176	0,6	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	176	1,7	3	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
trimethoprim	176	0,6	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	176	1,7	3	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				13	0,0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	176	93,8	165	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	1	100,0	1				13	100,0	13	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	176	4,0	7	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	1	0,0	0				13	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				13	0,0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	176	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				13	0,0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	176	0,6	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				13	0,0	0	

Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	73	2,7	2	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	73	4,1	3	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	73	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	73	2,7	2	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	73	2,7	2	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	73	83,6	61	113	99,1	112	5	20,0	1	47	97,9	46	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	73	4,1	3	113	2,7	3	5	0,0	0	47	2,1	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	73	8,2	6	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	73	83,6	61	113	99,1	112	5	20,0	1	47	97,9	46	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	73	72,6	53	113	91,2	103	5	20,0	1	47	93,6	44	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	73	75,3	55	113	91,2	103	5	20,0	1	47	93,6	44	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	
trimethoprim	73	9,6	7	113	1,8	2	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	73	15,1	11	113	0,9	1	5	80,0	4	47	2,1	1	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	73	6,8	5	113	8,0	9	5	0,0	0	47	4,3	2	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	73	5,5	4	113	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	73	58,9	43	113	83,2	94	5	20,0	1	47	91,5	43	1	100,0	1	3	66,7	2	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	73	8,2	6	113	6,2	7	5	0,0	0	47	2,1	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	73	5,5	4	113	1,8	2	5	0,0	0	47	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested			micro-biological resistant			total units tested			micro-biological resistant			total units tested			micro-biological resistant			
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	17	11,8	2	2	50,0	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	17	11,8	2	2	50,0	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	17	17,6	3	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	17	17,6	3	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
trimethoprim	17	5,9	1	2	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	17	82,4	14	2	50,0	1				1	100,0	1							
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	17	0,0	0	2	50,0	1				1	0,0	0							
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	17	11,8	2	2	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	17	5,9	1	2	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	17	0,0	0	2	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							

Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n																
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
trimethoprim	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n																
fully sensitive	7	100,0	7	5	100,0	5				2	100,0	2	1	100,0	1				
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0				2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0				2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0				2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0				2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	7	0,0	0	5	0,0	0				2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				

Table 27 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n															
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin																		
penicillins - ampicillin	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
polymyxins - colistin																		
quinolones - nalidixic acid	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	2	100,0	2
trimethoprim	6	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n															
fully sensitive	6	100,0	6							2	100,0	2	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	6	0,0	0							2	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	2	100,0	2
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	2	0,0	0

Table 28 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n																
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	100,0	1	
trimethoprim	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	3	66,7	2				1	0,0	0							1	0,0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							1	0,0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				1	100,0	1							1	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							1	0,0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	3	33,3	1				1	0,0	0							1	100,0	1	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0							1	0,0	0	

Table 29 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n															
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin																		
penicillins - ampicillin	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
polymyxins - colistin																		
quinolones - nalidixic acid	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
trimethoprim	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	0	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n															
fully sensitive	8	100,0	8	9	100,0	9				3	66,7	2				1	100,0	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0				3	33,3	1				1	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0				3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0				3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0				3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	8	0,0	0	9	0,0	0				3	0,0	0				1	0,0	0

Table 30 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n															
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	387	3,4	13	6	0,0	0	14	50,0	7	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	387	1,0	4	6	16,7	1	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	387	0,0	0	6	0,0	0	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	387	0,5	2	6	16,7	1	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	387	0,5	2	6	16,7	1	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	387	13,7	53	6	83,3	5	14	85,7	12	19	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	1	100,0	1
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	387	0,5	2	6	0,0	0	14	7,1	1	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin																		
penicillins - ampicillin	387	15,0	58	6	66,7	4	14	71,4	10	19	5,3	1	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
polymyxins - colistin																		
quinolones - nalidixic acid	387	12,4	48	6	83,3	5	14	85,7	12	19	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	1	100,0	1
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	387	15,2	59	6	33,3	2	14	64,3	9	19	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	1	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	387	16,0	62	6	33,3	2	14	78,6	11	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	100,0	1
trimethoprim	387	4,9	19	6	66,7	4	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n															
fully sensitive	387	76,5	296	6	16,7	1	14	7,1	1	19	94,7	18	7	85,7	6	1	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	387	6,2	24	6	0,0	0	14	14,3	2	19	5,3	1	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	387	3,4	13	6	16,7	1	14	0,0	0	19	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	1	100,0	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	387	5,7	22	6	33,3	2	14	21,4	3	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	387	3,4	13	6	0,0	0	14	7,1	1	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	387	4,9	19	6	33,3	2	14	50,0	7	19	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	1	0,0	0

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of cases of human campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,520 cases in 2014 and a slight decrease in 2015 with 6,259 cases. The number of *Campylobacter* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS by January 21, 2016. The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cows raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals show different colonization rates: broiler flocks around 60%, turkey flocks approx. 75%, pigs approx.. 50%, and cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are - securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned, cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data- determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak), to issue the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria, and preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes. The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of *Campylobacter*-prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* in broilers and turkey was performed according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out in 2014. In 2015 no specific program was foreseen in animals.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of *Campylobacter*-cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS as of January 21, 2016.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of *Campylobacter* spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37–42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level biochemical and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) were applied. The differentiation to species level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of campylobacteriosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegeseztz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria for the first time exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, campylobacteriosis (n = 6,259) was the most frequently notified food borne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für *Campylobacter*. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2015, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published by the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (BMGF) on a monthly and yearly basis and the annual report of the National Reference Centre. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 31 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015

Campylobacteriosis	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Cases	6,259	72.98	5,325	596	338
<i>C. jejuni</i>	5,195	60.57	4,458	460	277
<i>C. coli</i>	629	7.33	505	90	34
<i>C. lari</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>C. hyointestinalis</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified	433	5.05	361	45	27

Data source: EMS/NRL-C as of January 21, 2016

Table 32 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015

age groups	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.			<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>			<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified			other species		
	All *	M	F	All *	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	88	52	36	69	41	28	11	5	6	8	6	2	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	434	220	214	366	187	179	27	15	12	41	18	23	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	532	326	206	453	285	168	39	18	21	40	23	17	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1,291	695	596	1,075	586	489	129	66	63	87	43	44	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	1,752	885	866	1,478	754	723	173	78	95	100	53	47	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	1,239	727	512	1,010	605	405	154	83	71	75	39	36	0	0	0
65 years and older	923	472	451	744	382	362	96	51	45	82	38	44	1	1	1
All age groups	6,259	3,377	2,881	5,195	2,840	2,354	629	316	313	433	220	213	2	1	1

* in 1 case sex unknown

Table 33 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015

Month	<i>Campylobacter</i>				
	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. cases	<i>C. jejuni</i> cases	<i>C. coli</i> cases	<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified cases	other species cases
January	478	391	45	42	0
February	281	233	26	22	0
March	275	226	26	22	1
April	286	240	35	11	0
May	450	375	43	32	0
June	701	587	68	45	1
July	899	759	80	60	0
August	749	621	83	45	0
September	768	629	88	51	0
October	504	419	56	29	0
November	486	410	44	32	0
December	382	305	35	42	0
Total	6,259	5,195	629	433	2

4.2.3. *Campylobacter* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e.g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat and meat preparations from poultry and other foodstuffs.

Definition of positive finding

Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006. Isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry

(MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter: a concern to everyone*” was closed in June 2013. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. were assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria. The result of this platform has been published in: Konsensuspapier der bundesweiten Plattform *Campylobacter*, 17.1.2014 (German only).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Campylobacter should be added to microbiological criteria.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Fresh meat from broilers have been tested at different sampling stages. At processing plants and slaughterhouses 38 samples have been tested for *Campylobacter*, with 29 positive results (24 *C. jejuni*, 5 *C. coli*). This is a prevalence of 73.7% (CI: 58-85%), as 28 samples were positive due to the detection of *C. coli* and *C. jejuni* in one sample from a processing plant. In 2014 at processing plants and slaughterhouses 55.6% of the samples were *Campylobacter* positive. At the sampling stage retail 49 (30 *C. jejuni*, 19 *C. coli*) out of 82 samples have been positive for *Campylobacter* (59.8%, CI: 49-70%) in fresh broiler meat. In 2014, at retail the *Campylobacter* prevalence in fresh broiler meat was 68.9% (62 positive in 90 samples) compared to 59.8% (49 positive in 82 samples) in 2015. Fresh meat from turkey (at retail and catering) had a positivity rate of 32% (CI: 17-52%; 8 positive samples out of 25). In 2014 the positivity rate for fresh meat from turkey at retail and wholesale was 18%. In total, 43 meat preparations from unspecified poultry meat have been tested, with a prevalence of 34.9% (CI: 22-50%). One *Campylobacter jejuni* was detected at catering in the food category “other processed food products and prepared dishes” whereas in 35 raw milk samples, as well as in 129 other food samples of diverse food categories (meat, meat products, salad, fruits) no *Campylobacter* was found.

Additionally, 129 samples from fresh broiler meat samples from all sampling stages have been tested quantitatively (82 positive samples, but two isolates were found in one sample). In 6 samples > 1,000 CFU/g *Campylobacter* could be detected, 2 sample between 500 CFU/g and 1,000 CFU/g, 7 between 100 CFU/g and 500 CFU/g, 21 between 10 CFU/g and 100 CFU/g and 46 samples counted positive but <10 CFU/g. Comparing the rate of “high” *Campylobacter* positive samples (e.g. >500 CFU/g or >1.00 CFU/g) with previous years, no trend seems to be observable in broiler meat. A slightly decreasing prevalence rate in food has to be observed further in the next years.

The 25 fresh turkey meat samples have been tested quantitatively, and revealed one sample with 80 CFU/g, two samples with 30 CFU/g, the other five positive samples were below 10 CFU/g.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the respective chapter for foodborne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-15: *Campylobacter* spp. in food – Fruits and vegetable – non-pre-cut – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and catering companies by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables (like tomatoes, cucumbers, and berries (like strawberries, raspberries, ...))
fresh and frozen

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Campylobacter* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

75 samples were tested for *Campylobacter* spp.: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, VTEC and *Salmonella* spp.

Table 34 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	1	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
	Cutting plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	28	20	3	17	1
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	63	36	13	23	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	11	4	7	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	2	0	0	
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	9	2	7	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	
EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	1	1	0		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	1	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	5	2	3	0
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	5	0	0	5		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	3	2	1	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	6	1	5	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	5	1	4	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	1	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	1	1	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	6	4	2	0	
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	1	1	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	

Table 35 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - C. jejuni	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified	<i>Campylobacter</i> - Thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Bakery products - pastry		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
Egg products - liquid		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Eggs - table eggs		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Fruits		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	A-802-15	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fruits and vegetables - non-pre-cut	A-802-15	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	48	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Meat from pig - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	1	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0

4.2.4. *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

In 2015, no program to control *Campylobacter* in animals was foreseen.

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial susceptibility testing by broth microdilution method.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective agar at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under microaerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by biochemical methods and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility microtitre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, UK).

Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, 458 isolates of *Campylobacter* (411 *C. jejuni*, 47 *C. coli*) were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility using broth microdilution method. Compared to 2014, slight increases in resistance rates were observed for both, *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* to quinolones, ampicillin, and tetracycline; resistance to erythromycin was very low (0.5% in *C. jejuni*, 2% in *C. coli*).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The quinolone and tetracycline resistance rates of *C. jejuni* isolates from humans correspond with the resistance rates found in isolates from broiler meat.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The sentinel surveillance system will be continued. Results are published annually in the Report of the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter* and in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in poultry meat

Description of sampling designs

Sampling design has been described in the chapter “foodstuffs”, comprising samples of broiler and turkey meat/meat preparations and offals from the revision plan, scheduled samples and suspect samples, taken at retail or processing.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All isolates of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* that were sent to the NRL-AMR and for which the whole information needed for this reporting (e.g. sample stage, sample date, isolation date, etc.) was given, were susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter “foodstuffs”

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006. Isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

According to CID 2013/652/EU; testings are performed in the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

According to CID 2013/652/EU.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Isolates of *C. jejuni* from all broiler meat samples: 67 isolates have been tested: highest resistance rates were found towards quinolones (73%), followed by resistance to tetracyclines (43%) and ampicillin 30%. Low resistance was found towards streptomycin (3%) and no resistance was observed to gentamicin, chloramphenicol, imipenem, and erythromycin.

Isolates of *C. coli* from all broiler meat samples: 40 isolates have been tested: resistance rates were higher in *C. coli* isolates, 85% towards quinolones, 73% towards tetracyclines, 53% towards ampicillin, 15% towards streptomycin and 5% towards erythromycin. No resistance was observed to gentamicin, chloramphenicol, and imipenem.

Isolates of *C. jejuni* from all turkey meat samples: only 6 isolates were available for testing: 5 isolates showed resistance to quinolones and ampicillin, and 2 isolates resistance to tetracyclines.

Isolates of *C. coli* from all turkey meat samples: 12 isolates have been tested: 11 isolates showed resistance to quinolones, 10 to tetracyclines and ampicillin; one isolate each was resistant to erythromycin or to streptomycin.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, compared to previous years resistance rates in *C. jejuni* isolates from broiler meat showed slight increase in resistance to quinolones and tetracyclines.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

More investigations are needed.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* in animals

In 2015, no program was foreseen and performed.

Table 36 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli*, 2015

Antimicrobial	<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>		
	ECOFF	Range tested		ECOFF	Range tested	
	concentration (µg/ml)			concentration (µg/ml)		
	wild type ≤	lowest	highest	wild type ≤	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0,12	16	2	0,12	16
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	4	0,5	32	4	0,5	32
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	16	2	64	16	2	64
Carbapenems - Imipenem	8	0,06	16	8	0,06	16
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	0,5	0,06	32	0,5	0,06	32
Macrolides - Erythromycin	4	0,25	128	8	0,25	128
Penicillins – Ampicillin	8	1	64	8	1	64
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	16	2	256	16	2	256
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	0,12	64	2	0,12	64

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* this includes resistance to ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, streptomycin, erythromycin.

Table 37 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, qualitative data, 2015

	humans			broiler meat, fresh			Meat from broilers, meat preparation			Meat from broilers, offal			turkey meat, fresh		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	421	0,0%	0	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	421	1,9%	8	56	3,6%	2	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	421	0,2%	1	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	421	0,0%	0	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	421	73,9%	311	56	73,2%	41	10	70,0%	7	1	100,0%	1	6	83,3%	5
Macrolides - Erythromycin	421	0,5%	2	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	421	40,4%	170	56	26,8%	15	10	50,0%	5	1	0,0%	0	6	83,3%	5
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	421	73,2%	308	56	73,2%	41	10	60,0%	6	1	100,0%	1	6	66,7%	4
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	421	40,4%	170	56	42,9%	24	10	40,0%	4	1	100,0%	1	6	33,3%	2
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	421	24,2%	102	56	21,4%	12	10	30,0%	3	1	0,0%	0	6	16,7%	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	421	37,3%	157	56	39,3%	22	10	30,0%	3	1	100,0%	1	6	50,0%	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	421	36,1%	152	56	37,5%	21	10	40,0%	4	1	0,0%	0	6	33,3%	2
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	421	2,4%	10	56	1,8%	1	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	421	0,0%	0	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	421	0,0%	0	56	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *C. jejuni* this includes resistance to ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, streptomycin, erythromycin

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 38 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	humans
sampling context	cases

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
		%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048			
	N	%R	n	n																						
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	421	0,0%	0				265	146	10																	
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	421	1,9%	8						313	95	4	1	1	7												
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	421	0,2%	1								225	147	39	9	1											
Carbapenems - Imipenem	421	0,0%	0			335	80	6																		
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	421	73,9%	311		48	48	11	3			14	183	63	43	8											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	421	0,5%	2				19	172	169	58	1	1								1						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	421	40,4%	170							9	29	105	108	17	21	62	70									
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	421	73,2%	308								28	74	11			1	28	263	16							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	421	40,4%	170			43	140	43	25	4					6	22	138									

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 39 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, fresh, quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh
sampling context	

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	56	0,0%	0					31	24	1														
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	56	3,6%	2							36	18				2									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	56	0,0%	0									30	18	7	1									
Carbapenems - Imipenem	56	0,0%	0				46	9	1															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	56	73,2%	41			1	12	2				2	23	9	7									
Macrolides - Erythromycin	56	0,0%	0					1	23	23	8	1												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	56	26,8%	15								5	21	15		2	13								
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	56	73,2%	41									1	11	3				1	40					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	56	42,9%	24				6	19	4	3		1			2	21								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 40 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - meat preparation, quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation
sampling context	

Number of isolates available in the laboratory Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	10	0,0%	0					5	5															
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	10	0,0%	0							8	2													
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	10	0,0%	0									5	4	1										
Carbapenems - Imipenem	10	0,0%	0				7	1	2															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	10	70,0%	7				3							4	2	1								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	10	0,0%	0					1	5	3	1													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	10	50,0%	5								1			4			5							
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	10	60,0%	6									1	3						6					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	10	40,0%	4				1	2	2	1					1		1	2						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 41 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - offal, quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - offal
sampling context	

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
		%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0,0%	0																						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	1	0,0%	0																						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	1	0,0%	0																						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	1	0,0%	0																						
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	1	100,0%	1																						
Macrolides - Erythromycin	1	0,0%	0																						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	1	0,0%	0																						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	1	100,0%	1																						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	100,0%	1																						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 42 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey meat, fresh, quantitative data, 2015

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
		matrix	Meat from turkey - fresh
		sampling context	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	
antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant
	N	%R	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	6	0,0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	6	0,0%	0
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	6	0,0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	6	0,0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	6	83,3%	5
Macrolides - Erythromycin	6	0,0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	6	83,3%	5
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	6	66,7%	4
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	6	33,3%	2

	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
					3	3															
							3	3													
									1	4	1										
				3	3																
					1						2	2	1								
							1	3	1	1											
										1		1	4								
									1	1						4					
						2	1	1				1		1							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 43 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, qualitative data, 2015

	humans			broiler meat, fresh			Meat from broilers, meat preparation			Meat from broilers, offal			turkey meat, fresh			turkey meat, meat preparation		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	47	0,0%	0	33	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	47	10,6%	5	33	15,2%	5	6	16,7%	1	1	0,0%	0	10	10,0%	1	2	0,0%	0
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	47	0,0%	0	33	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	47	0,0%	0	33	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	47	85,1%	40	33	84,8%	28	6	83,3%	5	1	100,0%	1	10	90,0%	9	2	100,0%	2
Macrolides - Erythromycin	47	4,3%	2	33	6,1%	2	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	10,0%	1	2	0,0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	47	66,0%	31	33	54,5%	18	6	50,0%	3	1	0,0%	0	10	90,0%	9	2	50,0%	1
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	47	85,1%	40	33	84,8%	28	6	83,3%	5	1	100,0%	1	10	90,0%	9	2	100,0%	2
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	47	55,3%	26	33	72,7%	24	6	66,7%	4	1	100,0%	1	10	80,0%	8	2	100,0%	2
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	47	10,6%	5	33	3,0%	1	6	16,7%	1	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	47	34,0%	16	33	27,3%	9	6	16,7%	1	1	100,0%	1	10	30,0%	3	2	0,0%	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	47	46,8%	22	33	57,6%	19	6	50,0%	3	1	0,0%	0	10	50,0%	5	2	100,0%	2
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	47	6,4%	3	33	12,1%	4	6	16,7%	1	1	0,0%	0	10	20,0%	2	2	0,0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	47	2,1%	1	33	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	47	0,0%	0	33	0,0%	0	6	0,0%	0	1	0,0%	0	10	0,0%	0	2	0,0%	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 44 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>
matrix	humans
sampling context	sentinel

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
		%R	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	47	0,0%	0				2	37	8																	
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	47	10,6%	5						6	34	2						3	2								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	47	0,0%	0								5	30	10	2												
Carbapenems - Imipenem	47	0,0%	0			8	36	3																		
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	47	85,1%	40		3	3	1				1	5	21	10	3											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	47	4,3%	2				4	14	12	8	6	1						1	1							
Penicillins - Ampicillin	47	66,0%	31								1	4	11	16	3	2	10									
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	47	85,1%	40									7				2	22	16								
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	47	55,3%	26			2	8	4	5	2					1	2	23									

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 45 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat, fresh - quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh
sampling context	

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																					
		%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N																						
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	33	0,0%	0					28	5														
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	33	15,2%	5						3	23	1	1			3	2							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	33	0,0%	0								6	21	5	1									
Carbapenems - Imipenem	33	0,0%	0				10	22	1														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	33	84,8%	28			2	3					5	17	5	1								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	33	6,1%	2					5	12	5	7	1	1				2						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	33	54,5%	18									3	12	10	8								
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	33	84,8%	28									3	2				16	12					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	33	72,7%	24					7	1		1					24							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 46 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - meat preparation - quantitative data, 2015

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>																					
		matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation																					
		sampling context																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		%R	n	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	6	0,0%	0					3	3															
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	6	16,7%	1							3	2					1								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	6	0,0%	0								2	2	2											
Carbapenems - Imipenem	6	0,0%	0				1	5																
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	6	83,3%	5					1					3	2										
Macrolides - Erythromycin	6	0,0%	0					2	2		2													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	6	50,0%	3								2		1	2		1								
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	6	83,3%	5											1		1	1	3						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	6	66,7%	4					1			1						4							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 47 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - offal - quantitative data, 2015

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>																				
		matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - offal																				
		sampling context																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0,0%	0																				
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	1	0,0%	0																				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	1	0,0%	0																				
Carbapenems - Imipenem	1	0,0%	0																				
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	1	100,0%	1																				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	1	0,0%	0																				
Penicillins - Ampicillin	1	0,0%	0																				
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	1	100,0%	1																				
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	100,0%	1																				

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 48 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in turkey meat, fresh - quantitative data, 2015

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>																				
		matrix	Meat from turkey - fresh																				
		sampling context																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	10	0,0%	0					1	8	1													
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	10	10,0%	1							1	7	1				1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	10	0,0%	0								1	3	6										
Carbapenems - Imipenem	10	0,0%	0				1	3	4	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	10	90,0%	9						1				1	2	4	2							
Macrolides - Erythromycin	10	10,0%	1							2	4	3					1						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	10	90,0%	9										1			2	1	6					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	10	90,0%	9											1				1	4	4			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	10	80,0%	8							2							8						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 49 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in Meat from turkey - meat preparation - quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>
matrix	Meat from turkey - meat preparation
sampling context	

Number of isolates available in the laboratory

Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
		%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
	N	%R	n	n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0,0%	0																		
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	2	0,0%	0																		
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	2	0,0%	0																		
Carbapenems - Imipenem	2	0,0%	0																		
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	2	100,0%	2																		
Macrolides - Erythromycin	2	0,0%	0																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	2	50,0%	1																		
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	2	100,0%	2																		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	2	100,0%	2																		

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). In 2013, 36 cases in 2014, 49 cases were notified in the EMS, 47 in the NRC-L. In 2015, a slight decrease of cases was observed, 38 cases (EMS) or 37 cases (NRC-L). The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2 to 0.9). In 2015, lethality was reported in 12 out of 38 cases (32 % of cases). Due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. According to the NRC-L, isolates from 37 cases were typed, the 38-day lethality was 32 % (12 cases). This high fatality rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although raw milk, soft and semi-soft cheeses, ready-to-eat meat products, and smoked salmons are likely candidates as vehicles for infections. The source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately. Restrictions were tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases as well notified to the EMS as typed in the NRC-L.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria

or

- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the EMS, 38 cases of listeriosis were notified (as of January 25, 2016); due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. In the NRC-L, isolates from 37 cases were typed.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression.

Although dairy products and ready-to-eat meat and fish products are likely candidates as vehicles for the bacterium, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health (MOH). The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 50 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	38	0,44
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	23	0,27
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	5	0,06
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	0	0,00
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	8	0,09
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not typeable	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	1	0,01
Deaths	13	0,15
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	7	0,08
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	3	0,04
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	1	0,01
Congenital cases	1	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	1	

Data source: EMS as of January 25, 2016

Table 51 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-L), 2015

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	37	0,43
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	22	0,27
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	5	0,06
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	0	0,00
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	9	0,09
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b var.	1	0,01
Deaths	12	0,14
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	7	0,08
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	3	0,04
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	2	0,02
Congenital cases	1	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	1	

Data source: National Reference Centre for Listeria as of February 24, 2016

Table 52 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2015

	<i>Listeriosis</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2a			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not typeable/not specified		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	9	6	3	6	4	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
65 years and older	26	5	21	16	1	15	3	2	1	6	2	4	1	0	1
unknown	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
	38	11	26	23	5	18	5	3	2	8	3	5	2	0	1

Data source: EMS as of January 25, 2016

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Frequency of the sampling

At the production plant

The producer is responsible for the process hygiene. The frequency of sampling therefore depends on the critical control points of the specific product.

At retail

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

pasteurized and raw cows' milk, pig meat products, bovine meat products, fishery products, smoked fish, fruits and vegetables, etc.

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2004 and ISO 11290-2:2005

For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria* in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

Control program/mechanisms**Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases**

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria*. In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L.mono agar) and/or API, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available.

A serogroup-specific PCR according to Doumith et al. is performed routinely to differentiate the major *Listeria monocytogenes* serovars (Doumith et al., 2004). Further typing is carried out with PFGE or whole genome sequencing (Ruppitsch et al., 2015).

The PFGE profiles and/or the sequencing data of the strains are compared with the existing in house data base. In case of an outbreak these data can be immediately compared with international available databases or shared with other institutions on request.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food. This folder is available in German, Turkish and Serbo-Croatian (<http://www.ages.at/themen/krankheitserreger/listerien/>) and was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis. The Federal Ministry of Health published folders on their webpage (<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/buch/hygieneleitlinien/hygieneleitlinien.html>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, gynaecologists and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/7) or in raw cows' milk (0/27). Concerning pasteurised cows' milk no *Listeria* has been detected for six years (2010-2015). In total 609 cheeses were tested and *L. monocytogenes* could be detected in 4 samples (1-time >100 cfu/g, 1-time <100 cfu/g; the others below detection limit).

In 0 of 31 samples from pig meat products - paté (campaign A-803-15) and in 6 out of 88 samples (6.8 %) from mixed meat products *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found. 9 out of 241 samples (3.7 %) of red meat products (including campaign A-801-15) were found positive in 25 g and 1-time <100 cfu/g, and of red meat products - fermented sausages 11 out of 166 (6.6 %), 2-times >100 cfu/g, 1-time <100 cfu/g; the others below detection limit.

1.7 % of all samples from fishery products (3/177) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (all below detection limit). 1 out of 31 smoked fish samples (3.2 %) were found positive for *L. monocytogenes* below detection limit.

Other processed food products and prepared dishes added up to 697 samples of which 6 samples were found positive (0.9 %), all below detection limit.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the chapter foodborne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-801-15: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – sliced red meat products and poultry meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat; cheeses made from cows' milk – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March to September

Type of specimen taken

Sliced red meat products and poultry meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat and cheeses made from cows' milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

110 samples were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Additional information

None

Campaign A-802-15: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Fruits and vegetables – non-pre-cut – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables (like tomatoes, cucumbers), and berries (like strawberries, raspberries, ...), fresh and frozen

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

75 samples were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter* and VTEC

Campaign A-803-15: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – cheeses, spreadable and pig meat products - pâté – at catering and retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - August

Type of specimen taken

Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - spreadable, meat from pig - meat products - pâté

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

50 samples were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and VTEC.

Table 53 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2015

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x.g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk	Retail	AT	A-801-15	49	0	49	0	49	0	0
		EU	A-801-15	11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		XX	A-801-15	7	0	7	0	7	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	3	0	0
		XX		68	2	68	2	24	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		26	0	26	0	26	0	0
	Retail	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
EU			4	0	4	0	4	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		15	0	15	0	7	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		25	0	25	0	25	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		17	0	17	0	9	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		41	0	41	0	41	0	0
	Retail	AT		22	0	22	0	22	0	0
		EU		29	2	29	2	29	1	1
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		40	0	40	0	40	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 53 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 53 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - spreadable	Catering	AT	A-803-15	18	0	18	0	18	0	0
	Retail	AT	A-803-15	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Processing plant	AT		15	1	15	1	15	0	0
		AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Processing plant	AT		26	0	26	0	26	0	0
		AT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0
	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - buttermilk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		71	0	71	0	71	0	0
		AT		20	0	20	0	17	0	0
	Retail	EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		61	0	61	0	61	0	0
		AT		18	0	18	0	18	0	0
	Retail	EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Catering	AT		29	0	29	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		69	0	64	0	23	0	0
		AT		126	0	121	0	46	0	0
	Retail	EU		5	0	5	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		21	0	21	0	18	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		11	0	11	0	8	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	XX		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, goats' - UHT milk	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Table 54 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2015

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L.monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
	Retail	AT		49	2	49	2	47	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	4	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakery products - cakes	Catering	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		49	0	49	0	48	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	Catering	AT		25	0	25	0	24	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		109	0	109	0	108	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Chocolate	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Crustaceans - prawns	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans - shrimps	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans - shrimps - cooked	Retail	EU		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
Egg products	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Egg products - liquid	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 54 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fish - raw	Catering	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
		EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fish - smoked	Retail	AT		12	1	12	1	5	0	0
		EU		23	0	23	0	0	0	0
		XE		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - unspecified	Retail	EU		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	Catering	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		20	1	20	1	20	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		31	1	31	1	31	0	0
		EU		54	1	54	1	53	0	0
		XE		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
		XX		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
XE			3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		28	0	28	0	16	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fruits	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		EU		14	0	14	0	13	0	0
		XE		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0

Table 54 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	Retail	EU	A-802-15	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fruits - products	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fruits and vegetables - non-pre-cut	Retail	AT	A-802-15	48	0	48	0	0	0	0
		EU	A-802-15	23	0	23	0	0	0	0
		XE	A-802-15	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	EU		3	1	3	1	3	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products	Retail	AT		3	1	3	1	1	0	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from geese - meat preparation	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from horse - meat products	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0

Table 54 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - pâté	Catering	AT	A-803-15	26	0	26	0	26	0	0
	Retail	AT	A-803-15	5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
			A-801-15	4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		A-801-15	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT		2	2	2	2	2	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products	Processing plant	AT		49	5	49	5	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		27	1	27	1	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0

Table 54 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Catering	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		44	1	44	1	43	0	0
	Retail	AT		24	1	24	1	24	0	0
		EU		11	1	11	1	11	1	0
	Wholesale	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		12	1	12	1	12	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		44	3	44	3	44	0	0
	Retail	AT		44	2	44	2	44	0	0
		A-801-15		35	0	35	0	35	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		A-801-15		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	XX	A-801-15		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0
EU				1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Processing plant		AT		26	6	26	6	26	2	1
Retail		AT		39	2	39	2	39	0	0
		EU		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
		XX		67	2	67	2	32	0	0
Wholesale		AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	EU		11	0	11	0	11	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Mushrooms	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Nuts and nut products	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other food	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Table 54 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT		39	0	28	0	28	0	0
		EU		7	1	7	1	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		68	1	66	1	9	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		135	1	125	1	48	0	0
		EU		51	1	51	1	10	0	0
		XE		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
		XX		316	0	316	0	84	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		6	0	6	0	1	0	0
EU			5	1	5	1	3	0	0	
XE			2	0	2	0	1	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts	Retail	AT		41	0	41	0	41	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
		AT		7	0	7	0	0	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - frozen	Retail	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		18	0	18	0	13	0	0
	Retail	AT		24	0	24	0	11	0	0
Sauce and dressings	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Sweets	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Vegetables	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	8	0	9	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Vegetables - products	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic *Escherichia coli*

4.4.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2015, 107 laboratory confirmed VTEC cases were notified to the EMS. The number of cases was lower than in the last years (2014 and 2013: 130 cases; 2012: 127 cases; 2011: 129 cases). In the years 2007 to 2010 less cases were reported annually, between 88 to 103 cases. In 2015, out of the 107 cases, 15 cases of HUS were notified to the EMS.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease. The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC (the isolate of one case was not typed and confirmed in the NRL-VTEC).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2015, the monitoring of VTEC in animals has been ceased due to the high costs of the monitoring and lack of EU-co-financing.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was ceased after 11 years in 2015.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC (the isolate of one case was not typed and confirmed in the NRL-VTEC).

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing *E. coli*

- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- *E. coli* serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of *E. coli* O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the *E. coli* O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* are serotyped with *E. coli* antisera (*E. coli* antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of *E. coli* infection; however EHEC's themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 55 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
HUS	17	0.20	15	2	0
- caused by O157 (VT+)	7	0.08	6	1	0
- caused by other VTEC	8	0.09	7	1	0
- unknown serovar (no isolate obtained)	2	0.02	2	0	0
VTEC infect. (except HUS)	90	1.05	76	9	5
- caused by O157 (VT+)	29	0.34	24	3	2
- caused by other VTEC	45	0.52	40	3	2
- unknown serovar (no isolate obtained)	16	0.19	12	3	1
VTEC gesamt	107	1.25	91	11	5

Data source: EMS/NRL-VTEC as of June 21, 2016

Table 56 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2015

age groups	all VTEC infections			HUS		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	10	6	4	1	1	0
1 to 4 years	55	28	27	10	5	5
5 to 14 years	11	6	5	3	1	2
15 to 24 years	6	4	2	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	8	3	5	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	8	2	6	1	0	1
65 years and older	9	4	5	2	2	0
Gesamtergebnis	107	53	54	17	9	8

Data source: EMS/NRL-VTEC as of June 21, 2016

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations. In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen. Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e.g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, fruits, vegetables etc.

Defintion of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The sample is analyzed according to ISO/TS 13136.

There is no further testing for negative PCR results in the bacterial enrichment.

If the bacterial enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. At least 50 colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Center for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is tested by PCR.

Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera).

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

All isolates detected in food have to be sent to the National Reference Centre for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions taken.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

In 2015, in total 1.363 samples were tested for VTEC, 959 samples of animal origin, 150 samples of nonanimal origin and 252 samples of other processed food products and prepared dishes were tested for VTEC. 1 out of 172 (0.58%) samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows, sheeps or goats milk) were positive for VTEC O103:H2, which was a goats' raw milk sample. No positive findings were made in cheeses, dairy products or any other milk. Raw milk from cows at retail was tested 16 times for VTEC, without any positive findings. Comparing these results with previous years, less VTEC was found in milk, milk products and cheeses.

221 samples of fresh meat of several animals (bovine animals, deer, pig, rabbit, sheep, wild boar) were tested for VTEC resulting in 16 positive samples (7.2%). The highest prevalence of VTEC was detected in fresh meat from sheep in 28.6% (2 out of 7). In 2014, in 13 out of 37 fresh meat samples from deer (venison) resulted in 35.1% positivity rate for VTEC, whereas in 2015 the prevalence was 12.8% (5 out of 39 samples of fresh meat from deer).

383 samples of meat products of several animals were tested for VTEC showing 11 positives. All vegetables, fruits, herbs (were negative for VTEC).

All serovars have been detected once, but two VTEC O21:H21 were identified in "meat from other species or not identified".

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-15: VTEC in food – Fruits and vegetable – non-pre-cut – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and catering companies by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables (like tomatoes, cucumbers, and berries (like strawberries, raspberries, ...) fresh and frozen

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25 g

Results of the investigation

75 samples were tested for VTEC: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* spp.

Campaign A-803-15: VTEC in food – cheeses, spreadable and pig meat products – pâté – at catering and retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and catering companies by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July to August

Type of specimen taken

Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - spreadable, meat from pig - meat products - pâté

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25 g

Results of the investigation

50 samples were tested for VTEC: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* spp.

Table 57 cont.

Food		Sampling Details		Sampling Stage		Sampling Origin		Sampling Unit		Sample Weight		Sampling Weight Unit		Total Units tested		Total Units positive		zoonosisTerm		Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC)																					
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																				
																						Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
																																									25
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																				
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)	Cutting plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																				
																						Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																			
																							Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					Retail	AT		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					Wholesale	AT		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					25	Gram	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																					
																					Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

4.4.4. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in animals

A. Verotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* in cattle (bovine animals)

No program in 2015.

B. Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in animal – Sheep

No program in 2015

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free. In humans the number of tuberculosis cases is decreasing. Cases of *M. bovis* or *M. caprae* are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. In 2015, three *M. caprae* cases in humans were found, two of them showing the same molecular typing patterns as the *M. caprae* isolated from cattle.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. In spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intracutaneous testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reactors were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae*, 2011 three cases were found to be positive for *M. caprae*. In 2013, ten bovines out of five herds were infected with *M. caprae*. In 2014, 11 bovines out of 10 herds were diagnosed with *M. caprae*. In 2015, 5 bovines out of 4 herds were diagnosed with *M. caprae*. For several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in three western alpine Austrian regions has been confirmed. Epidemiological connection to the situation in wild deer could be confirmed in all cases of tuberculosis in cattle. Most infected cattle were infected directly during summer pasture in the above mentioned alpine regions.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. In 2015, two isolates of *M. caprae* from humans showed the same molecular typing results as *M. caprae* isolates from animals in Western Austria.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 a new regulation has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer (BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011). The regulation (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322) obliges the intracutaneous testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation. All animals which were on transhumance in endangered regions are obligatorily tested for tuberculosis after return to their home holding. In case of positive findings all appropriate measures are taken.

Measures are also taken by hunters in the infected areas which include reduction of wild deer population and change in winter feeding management.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Three cases each of *M. bovis* and *M. caprae* were identified; two isolates of *M. caprae* from humans showed the same molecular typing results as *M. caprae* isolates from animals in Western Austria.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

For each case esp. of *M. caprae* the infectious source has to be investigated.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and the annual report of the National Reference Center for tuberculosis.

Table 58 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-Tbc), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	cases with place of birth Austria	cases with place of birth other than Austria
Tuberculosis	437	5,08	137	300
<i>M. bovis</i>	3	0,03	1	2
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	393	4,58	122	271
<i>M. caprae</i>	3	0,03	3	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)	37	0,43	11	26
Other species (<i>M. africanum</i>)	1	0,01	0	1
Reactivation of previous cases	-*	-	-	-

* Available data unreliable

Data source: National Reference Center for tuberculosis as of April 15, 2016

Table 59 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution (NRC-Tbc), 2015

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis complex</i> (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	8	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	74	55	19	2	1	1	0	0	0	8	7	1
25 to 44 years	139	90	49	1	0	1	0	0	0	11	7	4
45 to 64 years	99	72	27	0	0	0	2	1	1	6	2	4
65 years and older	71	50	21	0	0	0	1	0	1	12	7	5
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	393	271	122	3	1	2	3	1	2	37	23	14

Data source: National Reference Center for tuberculosis as of April 15, 2016

4.5.3. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animals

A. *Mycobacterium bovis* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - Free regions

All regions

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EEC from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free (OTF) Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. Therefore, as of May 2000 the nationwide intradermal testing has been suspended and the disease is now monitored as a part of ante- and post mortem inspection of all bovine animals and goats (which were kept together with bovines) slaughtered.

According to the national Regulation Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all *Mycobacteria* belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTC) are compulsory notifiable. The Rindertuberkuloseverordnung shall apply to bovine animals and to goats (which are kept together with bovine animals) slaughtered.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

According to the monitoring system of ante and post mortem inspection of slaughtered animals, samples are taken from carcasses which show pathological-anatomical alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis at slaughterhouse. Laboratory examination and diagnosis is done by the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Moedling).

Subsequent to the detection of *M. caprae* positive cases in wild red deer in specific areas of the federal provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg since 2008 the BMGF (Federal Ministry of Health) orders annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

After official announcement testing is carried out in special testing zones and special monitoring zones of risk including all animals older than 6 months (cattle and goats kept together with bovines) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Sampling is carried out according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Moedling).

Monitoring system - Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung tuberculosis is defined as an infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Live bovine animals and goats: Intradermal testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008). A reactor is an animal which does not show a negative (either doubtful or positive) result to intradermal testing.

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture is performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for tuberculosis in animals in Moedling. After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2 g, homogenized, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörensen Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500 g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD: Loewenstein-Jensen and Stonebrink agar containing antibiotics). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany). Genotyping of isolates is undertaken using molecular biological methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), spoligotyping and MIRU-VNTR (mycobacterial interspersed repetitive unit variable number tandem repeat) analysis.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Subsequent to the detection of *M. caprae* positive cases in wild red deer in specific areas of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg since 2008 the BMGF (Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs) orders annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (special testing zones and special monitoring zones) according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all live animals suspected being infected shall be killed for diagnostic purposes (including sampling for laboratory investigation). All animals suspected post mortem at slaughter of being infected shall be subject to laboratory investigation. All animals of the holding of origin of animals suspected of being infected must be tested immediately (simultaneous intradermal test) and epidemiologic investigations must be carried out. The status of disease freedom of the holding which is suspected of being infected is suspended and subsequently withdrawn in case of confirmation of the disease and the holding is banned immediately after suspicion. Milk from such holdings shall be used for human consumption only according to the specifications laid down in Annex III, Section IX, Chapter I of the Regulation EC no. 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin or shall be used after boiling for feeding the animals of the affected holding only. The status freedom of disease of an

infected holding is regained after culling of all animals that did not reveal a negative result and disinfection under official control.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

See Other preventive measures in place.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions to EU

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place.

Notification system in place

The notification of bovine animals and goats kept together with bovines suspected of being infected is compulsory.

Results of the investigation

In 2015, *M. bovis* was not detected in cattle. Although in total, 5 bovines from 4 herds were diagnosed as infected with *M. caprae*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In 2015, an infection with *M. caprae* could be confirmed in 5 bovines originating from 4 herds located in the western part of Austria. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in red deer in certain areas of the western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), the testing of bovines and goats (which are kept together with bovines) according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung within special testing zones and special monitoring zones will be carried on for the time being.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In case of the suspicion of the disease in a holding, all measures which shall be taken according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung shall be notified in written to the zoonosis coordinator of the province affected by.

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria. The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure. See also the publication: Fink M, Schleicher C, Gonano M, Prodingner WM, Pacciarini M, Glawischnig W, et al., 2015. Red deer as maintenance host for bovine tuberculosis, Alpine Region. Emerg Infect Dis [Internet]. 2015 Mar [date cited]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid2103.141119>.

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system – Sampling strategy

According to the federal law for zoonoses (BGBl. I no. 2005/128) following shall be subject to monitoring: tuberculosis caused by *M. bovis* and tuberculosis caused by other than *M. bovis* according to the epidemiological situation.

According to federal law Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I no. 13/2016) and the Regulation Tierseuchen-Untersuchungspflicht-Verordnung BGBl. II no. 90/2007) all slaughter animals shall be subject to ante and post-mortem inspection. Samples from tuberculosis suspected animals are taken after slaughter. Tissues of slaughtered animals which are visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye and lymph nodes.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken

Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymph nodes

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the AGES Moedling, NRL for tuberculosis in animals.

Monitoring system – Case definition

According to the Regulation (EC) no 854/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture is performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for tuberculosis in animals in Moedling. After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2 g, homogenized, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörensen Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500 g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD: Loewenstein-Jensen and Stonebrink agar containing antibiotics). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany). Genotyping of isolates is undertaken using molecular biological methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), spoligotyping and MIRU-VNTR (mycobacterial interspersed repetitive unit variable number tandem repeat) analysis.

Preventive measures in place**Vaccination policy**

Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms – The control program/strategies in place

The control strategy is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all animals slaughtered.

Control program/mechanisms – Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Control program/mechanisms – Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions to EU

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Measures are taken according to the Regulation (EC) no 854/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

M. bovis was not detected in any animal tested.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases of *M. bovis* in Austria in 2015.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 60 Bovine tuberculosis in 2015

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 24.06.2016..... Year: 2015.....

The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes

Region (¹)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds*		Infected herds*		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(1)(2)(c) third indent (¹) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination (* <i>M. caprae</i>)
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (²)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	63,476	1,965,618	63,472	99.9937	4	0.0063	a) and (g)	42,762	26	46	5
Total	63,476	1,965,618	63,472	99.9937	4	0.0063	a) and (g)	42,762	26	46	5

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

* Additional information: In 2015, in 5 bovines out of 4 herds an infection with *M. caprae* could be confirmed. The control measures for *M. caprae* are the same as for *M. bovis*.

Table 61 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2015

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> complex	<i>M. bovis</i>	<i>M. caprae</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	136,256	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	7,763	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,381,689	0	0	0

CVS: Central veterinary services

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially *Brucella melitensis* free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One human case was identified in 2015. This case was an imported case. The number of brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and blood-samples in cattle (Bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on *Brucella* agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 62 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>Brucella</i> spp.	1	0.01	0	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL-B (as of 18.01.2016)

Table 63 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2015

Age group	Brucellosis			Brucella unspecified		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	1	1	-	1	1	-
45 to 64 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
65 years and older	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	1	1	0	1	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL-B (as of 18.01.2016)

4.6.3. *Brucella* in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for *Brucella* spp.

4.6.4. *Brucella* spp. in animals

A. *Brucella abortus* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year - Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds. A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and blood-samples in cattle (Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In milk producing holdings and non-milk producing holdings a risk based blood sampling plan was performed. Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Holdings with and without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated. If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

Abortion or premature birth in context with epidemiological investigation: must be notified to the district veterinarian (§7 and §25 of Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Tissues from the aborted fetus and blood from the affected cows are sampled immediately post abortion and tested for brucellosis by microbiological and serological methods.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Aborted fetus

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Based on: Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Bulk milk sampling and in holdings without milk production blood samples are taken according to the risk based sampling plan. Samples are sent to approved laboratories (according to Annex A of regulation).

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to the NRL.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for bovine brucellosis, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a *Brucella abortus*-infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get sufficient information about the reacting animal.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwPSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE Brucella abortus Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the I-ELISA single serum samples were tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and two ELISAs for verification.

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (AHVLA, ANSES) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for those Austrian Veterinary Institutes which are involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnosis.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforths method. Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were inoculated. The culture media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Laboratories are accredited according to EN ISO/IEC 17025.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (§6 Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Abortion or premature birth: compulsory notification according §7 and §25 Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to the Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth; Notification of abortions in context with epidemiological investigations: Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013 and Venereal diseases act, Federal Law Gazette no. 22/1949 as amended; The livestock owner has to notify the abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the district veterinarian (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde).

Results of the investigation

In 2015, no cases detected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not of relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Brucella melitensis* in sheep and goats

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - Free regions

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - Additional information

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

The entire country is free of *B. melitensis*. According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially *B. melitensis* free (ObmF). To maintain that status according to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Ueberwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. In cases of abortion, aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal were also investigated. The above mentioned Regulation has been replaced by the Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 as from 1 November 2015.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

The sampling was performed mainly during the cold season, between November and May when the animals have been kept in the stables.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.

Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the approved laboratories.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or a positive serological test result.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from AHVLA and ANSES. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforths method. Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Laboratories are accredited according to EN ISO/IEC 17025.

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Ueberwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) replaced by the Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015, § 21, as from 1 November 2015 vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Ueberwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002 replaced by the Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 as from 1 November 2015) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings. Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Federal Law Gazette no 1995/391 (Brucellosis Regulation) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 391/1995 (Brucellose-Verordnung).

Results of the investigation

In 2015, no cases detected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Additional information

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

No monitoring program, only targeted, following abortion and in positive cases of contact holdings.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring: Blood samples;

Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the approved laboratories.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Brucella ELISA and CFT are used.

Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (AHVLA and ANSES) with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: - Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforths method.- Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Laboratories are accredited according to EN ISO/IEC 17025.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No other measures foreseen

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

There was no case of *Brucella suis* in 2015.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

Currently of no relevance in Austria

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 64 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing (non co-financed), 2015

Member State: Austria Date of report: 24.06.2016..... Year: 2015.....

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
Austria	63,476	1,965,618	63,476	100	0	0	1,329	11,753	0	1,345	1,345	0	344	0	0	517	11	0	0	165	0
Total	63,476	1,965,618	63,476	100	0	0	1,329	11,753	0	1,345	1,345	0	344	0	0	517	11	0	0	165	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 65 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2015

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 24.06.2016..... Year: 2015.....

Region (¹)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (²)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	25,864	549,271	25,864	100	0	0	1,543	19,216	0	10	0	0	0	10
Total	25,864	549,271	25,864	100	0	0	1,543	19,216	0	10	0	0	0	10

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprine herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed (NRC-Y) cases notified to the EMS.

The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed (NRC-Y) cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Y. enterocolitica* or *Y. pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3; O:5,27; O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBI. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the fourth most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In Austria yersiniosis is much less identified than salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 66 Yersiniosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2015

Yersiniosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
cases	106	1,23
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4	91	1,06
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2	14	0,16
<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	1	0,01

Data source: EMS/NRC-Y as of 19.1.2016

Table 67 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2015

age groups	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2			<i>Y.</i> <i>pseudotuberculosis</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	9	5	4	5	2	3	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	22	15	7	1	1	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	18	10	8	3	2	1	1	1	0
25 to 44 years	25	10	15	3	1	2	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	12	8	4	1	1	0	0	0	1
65 years and older	4	1	3	1	1	0	0	0	0
Gesamtergebnis	91	49	42	14	8	6	1	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRC-Y as of 19.1.2016

4.7.3. *Yersinia* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: EN ISO 10273:2003 in combination with the PCR Screening: ISO/TS 18867.

Results of the investigation

See table below

Table 68 *Yersinia* spp. in food, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Yersinia</i>
Meat from pig - fresh		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	1
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0

4.7.4. *Yersinia* spp. in animals

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place

Findings of *Yersinia* are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochthone human infestations in 2015.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2015, no cases in animals that were used for food production, farmed or wild, were detected.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of *Trichinella* larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- *Trichinella* specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 69 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	0	0.00	0	0
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	0	0.00	0	0

Data source: EMS as of February 12, 2015

4.8.3. *Trichinella* spp. in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition

Trichinella sp. detected with one of the given methods.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No other preventive measures.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No recent actions.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Notification system in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings in horses.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No cases in humans diagnosed in 2015.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about *Trichinella* investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for *Trichinella*.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition

Trichinella sp. detected with one of the given methods.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place****Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

In 2015 no case of *Trichinella* was found neither in farmed nor in wild wild boars.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015 no case of *Trichinella* was found neither in farmed nor in wild wild boars.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No cases in humans diagnosed in 2015.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in pigs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - General

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - General

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition - General

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - General

According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Preventive measures in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Summary results of the inspections of *Trichinella*-free holdings including information on farmer compliance

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No recent actions.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Each detected case must be notified to the authority.

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed pigs

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed pigs.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in humans diagnosed in 2015.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 70 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2015

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,381,689	0
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	783	0
Wild boars							
Wild boars, wild	hunting	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	25,406	0
Wild boars, farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	769	0
Nutria							
				CVS	animal	2	0
Badger							
				CVS	animal	1	0

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *E. granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test
- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *E. granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 71 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	8	0,09	3	2	3
<i>E. granulosus</i>	4	0.05	1	1	2
<i>E. multilocularis</i>	4	0.05	2	1	1

Data source: EMS as of January 18, 2016

Table 72 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2015

Age group	<i>E. multilocularis</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	3	1	2	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	0	0	0	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	0	0	0	2	1	1
65 years and older	1	1	0	1	1	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	4	2	2	4	2	2

Data source: EMS as of January 18, 2016

4.9.3. *Echinococcus* spp. in animals

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Monitoring system - Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Carcasses with very low number of detected cysts are made fit for consumption by deep-freezing overseen by the official veterinarian; if higher numbers of cysts are found the carcasses are declared unfit for human consumption.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in the last years.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No information available.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 73 *Echinococcus* sp. in animals, 2015

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Echinococcus</i> spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle*	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	695,174	117	-	-	117
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	136,256	212	-	-	212
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	7,763	0	-	-	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,381,689	2	-	-	2

* cattle including calves

x: Central Veterinary Services

All detected cysts are reported as echinococcus but not differentiated (could also be other species than *Echinococcus* spp.).

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.2. *Toxoplasma* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. To determine the incidence of primary gestational infections with *Toxoplasma gondii* and congenital toxoplasmosis in Austria, a nationwide prenatal serological screening program exists since 1974, the Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register. In Austria, *Toxoplasma* screening of pregnant women is part of the “motherchild-booklet” and covered by national healthcare providers and the Ministry of Health.

First-line serologic screening is scheduled within the first trimester, and analyses are performed by clinical laboratories. Seronegative women have to be retested bimonthly. In case of primary gestational infection (PGI), treatment is administered until birth.

Case definition

Women with seroconversions and potential infections were classified as having PGI. Infants were classified as follows: (1) congenital toxoplasmosis, determined by the persistence of anti-*Toxoplasma* immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies beyond the age of 1 year, positive PCR from amniotic fluid, or histopathological isolation of parasite; or (2) non-infected infants, with maternally transmitted antibodies, identified by negative *Toxoplasma*-specific IgG during the first year of life.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Since 1992, amniocentesis and *Toxoplasma*-specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) have been used for diagnosis in affected women and to determine treatment management. If *Toxoplasma* was detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Serum samples were analyzed routinely by different automated test systems in clinical laboratories. In general, all institutions were certified for quality management according to the International Organization for Standardization from Quality Austria. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up. In case of undetermined infection status, the in-house Sabin-Feldman dye test and immunoglobulin M immunosorbent agglutination assay (bioMérieux) were performed at the Reference Laboratory. The PCR analyses of amniotic fluid samples were only performed with the same protocol at the Medical University of Vienna

Notification system in place

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In this 17-year period, 1992-2008, congenital toxoplasmosis incidence of 8.45 (95% CI, 7.98–8.95) PGIs per 10,000 women, and 1.0 (95% CI, 0.84–1.18) per 10,000 births was reported. Incidence of symptomatic congenital toxoplasmosis was 0.12 per 10,000 live births. This resulted in a mean transmission rate of 13%. In detail, the transmission was <9% (95% CI, 2.9%–14.2%) In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth. Congenital toxoplasmosis was confirmed in 141 cases, resulting in a morbidity of 1.4% (95% CI, 0.83%–2.27%) and mortality of

0.6% (95% CI, 0.24%–1.20%). In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth.

Results of the investigation

In 2015, maternally infections were diagnosed in 83 cases, congenital toxoplasmosis in seven cases. Three more patients are still under antiparasitic treatment but the infectious status has not been confirmed due to age (< 9 months).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register reveals a decrease of the incidence of congenital toxoplasmosis since the implementation of the mandatory prenatal screening compared with historical data. Prior to screening, the rate of congenital toxoplasmosis was 78 per 10,000 live births. In the 17-year study period, the authors of the study (see additional information) observed a decrease of congenital toxoplasmosis to 1 per 10,000 births. In addition, they found 9 per 10,000 PGIs per year.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Toxoplasmosis is a relevant zoonotic disease, because infection only occurs via orally ingestion of oocysts after contact with cats and food contaminated with cat faeces or via consumption of cysts-containing undercooked or raw meat.

Additional information

The information about “*Toxoplasma* in humans” is taken from: Prusa AR, Kasper DC, Pollak A, Gleiss A, Waldhoer T, Hayde M (2015) The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, 1992-2008. Clin Infect Dis. 2015 Jan 15;60(2)

Table 74 Toxoplasmosis cases in pregnant and fetus (NRL-T), 2015

	N
Maternally infections	83
Congenital cases	7*

* 3 more patients are still under antiparasitic treatment but the infectious status has not been confirmed due to age (< 9 months)

Data source: National Toxoplasmosis Register as of June 6, 2016
 (Toxoplasmose Diagnostik in der Schwangerschaft und kindliches Follow-up
 Nationales Toxoplasmose Register
 Klinische Abteilung für Neonatologie, pädiatrische Intensivmedizin und Neuropädiatrie
 Univ. Klinik für Kinder- und Jugendheilkunde
 Medizinische Universität Wien
 1090 Wien, Währinger Gürtel 18-20)

4.10.3. *Toxoplasma* in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma gondii* in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, fetus, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically or by PCR. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the direct agglutination test. Organs are tested by real time PCR and/or histology and/or immunohistochemistry (IHC).

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Control programme/ mechanisms:**The control programmes/ strategies in place**

Nil

Notification system in place:

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

see table

Table 75 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2015

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Analytical method	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma
bovine	privat sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	2	0
bovine	routine sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	3	0
bovine	suspected sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	21	0
sheep	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	8	1
sheep	privat sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	8	5
sheep	routine sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	12	0
sheep	routine sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	4	7
pig	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
goat	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	3	0
goat	privat sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	5	4
goat	routine sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	14	2
goat	routine sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	1	0

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2015, no case of rabies was detected in humans or animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not of relevance

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2015, due to official rabies free status in Austria (since 28.9.2008) oral vaccination of foxes has been suspended; monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union" (<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/doc/67e.pdf>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not of relevance

Additional information

Not of relevance

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus neutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No case in Austria in 2015

Table 76 Rabies in humans, 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human exposure	0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 27, 2016

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Wild animals: According to the degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012) monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect).

Other animals: Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Wild animals: Monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union.

Other animals: If a case is suspected

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Brain (brain stem and/or hippocampus)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Wild animals: Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm) is examined.

Other animals: Routinely 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test is the fluorescent antibody test (FAT). RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) is performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells. MIT (mouse inoculation test) is only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation.

Vaccination policy

Due to official status rabies free no vaccination of foxes. Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Wild animals: Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten; degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012).
Other animals: According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not of relevance

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not of relevance

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42, and vaccination of the fox population. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

No positive results

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria has been declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No positive results

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No positive results

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies. In 2013, oral vaccination of foxes was suspended all over Austria.

Table 77 Rabies in animals, 2015

Animal species	Sampling stage	Sampling context	sampler	Sampling strategy	Sample type	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Foxes – wild*	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	101	0
Foxes - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	109	0
Badgers – wild*	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	17	0
Badgers - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	5	0
Bats - wild	Unspecified	Monitoring - passive	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	59	0
Dogs - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	37	0
Cats - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	32	0
Deer - wild - roe deer	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Cattle (bovine animals) – unspec.	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Solipeds, domestic - horses	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	8	0
Marten - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	13	0
Hamster - pet	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Rabbit - pet	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Dormouse - pet	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0

Immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT) and/or PCR and/or cell culture

* indicator animals(foxes,badgers,racoons,racoon dogs food dead, victims of road traffic) according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union"

Data source: NRL-Rabies as of 27.04.2016

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs are tested by real time PCR or immunohistochemistry (IHC) and swabs by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

There is no official surveillance program therefore no representative results for Austria are available.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 78 Q-fever in animals, 2015

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Analytical method	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
horse	privat sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
bovine	export sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	146	0
bovine	privat sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	568	6
bovine	privat sample	milk	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	4	4
bovine	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	80	4
bovine	routine sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	78	3
bovine	routine sample	organs	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	38	4
bovine	suspected sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	26	0
sheep	privat sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	3,373	59
sheep	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	8	2
sheep	routine sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	6	0
sheep	routine sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	17	2
goat	export sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	278	0
goat	privat sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	5	0
goat	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	3	0
goat	routine sample	blood	complement fixation reaction	animal	AGES IVET	3	0
goat	routine sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	19	1

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. *E. coli* Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from different slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004. In 2015, the AMR-monitoring for indicator *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Animals: In isolates from pigs, high resistance rates were detected towards tetracyclines (47%) and sulphonamides (23%), moderate rates towards ampicillin (13%) and trimethoprim (10%).

Resistance rates to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, chloramphenicol, cefotaxime, ceftazidime and gentamicin were low (4.9%, 3.1%, 3.7%, 2.5%, 1.8%, and 2.5%). One isolate showed resistance to colistin (0.6%); no resistance was found towards meropenem, tigecycline and azithromycin.

Four of the indicator *E. coli*-isolates were resistant against 3rd generation cephalosporins. Those isolates were tested in the panel 2. Three isolates were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

Out of 257 caecals samples from pigs tested, 134 suspected ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were identified and susceptibility tested. 117 isolates showed resistance to both 3rd generation cephalosporins, 17 were resistant only against cefotaxime. 124 isolates were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*, 10 isolates as AmpC-producing *E. coli*.

Out of 247 caecal samples from pigs, carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any sample.

Food:

Pork: Out of 224 samples, 22 suspected Enzyme-producing *E. coli* were isolated. In total, 19 ESBL-producing and one AmpC-producing *E. coli* were confirmed.

216 samples of fresh pig meat were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

Beef: In 7 out of 234 samples suspected Enzyme-producing *E. coli* were detected, all seven were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

226 samples of fresh beef were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolates from animals

A. Antimicrobial resistance of indicator *E. coli* from pigs at slaughterhouse

Description of sampling designs

The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator *E. coli* and enzyme-producing *E. coli*) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator - *E. coli* is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for enzyme-producing *E. coli* was given). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample (all samples on indicator-*E. coli* were simultaneously tested on enzyme-producing *E. coli*).

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 17 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all fattened and slaughtered pigs in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing *E. coli* (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing *E. coli*). To save resources, as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample, therefore, 180 of these samples were also tested for the indicator *E. coli*. In recent years, *E. coli* were isolated from 96% of caeca of pigs. A sample size of 180 samples would guarantee 170 required *E. coli* isolates with 90% probability.

For stratification procedures the number of slaughtered pigs per abattoir 2013 and 2014 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month.

In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first indicator-*E. coli* isolate or first enzyme-producing *E. coli*).

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter Stratification procedures

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Samples from 227 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 38 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range ($> 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $< 8^{\circ}\text{C}$). If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 14 test results had to be discarded because the caeca originated from fattening pigs' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. Remaining 175 samples.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

A piece of caecum, ligated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Immediately after evisceration a piece of caecum per sampled carcass was ligated, cut and placed in a sterile bag. Prior to dispatch the sample was cooled down to 2-4°C. The sample was dispatched in a polystyrene box with frozen cold packs to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

175 samples were regularly tested, 163 indicator-*E. coli* could be isolated. All 163 isolates were antimicrobial susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

A sample form was completed by the vet at the abattoir and sent together with the sample to the laboratory. In the laboratory all information was entered into the data base (LISA), also the lab results. The whole file with all data could be downloaded and analyzed using MS Excel®.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Suspect *E. coli* colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

According to CID 2013/652/EU; testings are performed in the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

According to CID 2013/652/EU.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of all 163 indicator *E. coli* tested, 85 isolates (52.2%) showed microbiological resistance to one or more antimicrobial substances tested. Twenty-three isolates (14.1%) were resistant to 3 or more antimicrobial classes. High resistance rates could be observed to tetracycline (47.2%) and sulfonamides (22.7%), moderate rates to ampicillin (12.9%) and trimethoprim (10.4%). Resistance rates to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, chloramphenicol, cefotaxime, ceftazidime and gentamicin were low (4.9%, 3.1%, 3.7%, 2.5%, 1.8%, and 2.5%). One isolate showed resistance to colistin (0.6%); towards the other antimicrobial substances no resistances were found.

Four isolates were resistant against 3rd generation cephalosporins. Those isolates were tested in the panel 2. Three isolates were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Since 2013, when indicator *E. coli* from pigs have been susceptibility tested for the last time, the situation has been improved. In 2013, 30% of isolates were sensitive to all antimicrobial substances tested, in 2015, 48% were fully sensitive. Microbiological resistance against tetracyclines decreased from 53% in 2013 to 47% in 2015, against sulfonamides from 29% to 23%, against ampicillin from 17% to 13%, against trimethoprim from 15% to 10%. Microbiological resistance to all other substances remained low below 5%. High resistance rates (57%) have been found towards streptomycin in 2013 but this substance has been deleted from the panel acc. to CID 2013/652/EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from pigs at slaughterhouse

Description of sampling designs

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Samples from 344 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 65 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range ($> 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $< 8^{\circ}\text{C}$). If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 22 test results had to be discarded because the caeca originated from fattening pigs' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. All remaining 257 samples were analysed.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

257 samples were regularly tested; suspected isolates of Enzyme-producing *E. coli* were detected in 134 samples (52.1%). All 163 isolates were antimicrobial susceptibility tested. All 134 isolates were antimicrobial susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocol: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 1 and 2"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Notification system in place

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Results of the investigation

134 suspected ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were susceptibility tested. 117 isolates showed resistance to both 3rd generation cephalosporins, 17 were resistant only against cefotaxime. 124 isolates were confirmed as ESBL- producing *E. coli*, 10 isolates as AmpC- producing *E. coli*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring was performed for the first time therefore no statement concerning trends over time can be made.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Molecular typing results will show which and how many of the isolated enzyme-producing *E. coli* can also be found in human samples.

Additional information

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

C. Antimicrobial resistance of Carbapenemase producing *E. coli* from pigs at slaughterhouse

Description of sampling designs

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Out of the remaining 257 samples that were tested for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*, 247 were also screened for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

There were no isolates found that were suspected for carbapenemase-production.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocoll: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. October 2015, Version 1 and 2"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

See chapter "*E. coli* in pigs"

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

See chapter “*E. coli* in pigs”

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See chapter “*E. coli* in pigs”

Notification system in place

See chapter “*E. coli* in pigs”

Results of the investigation

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any caecal sample from pigs.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any caecal sample from pigs.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any caecal sample from pigs.

Additional information

See chapter “*E. coli* in pigs”

AMR *E. coli* animals (calves at slaughterhouse)

value

D. Antimicrobial resistance of indicator *E. coli* from bovines under one year at slaughterhouse

Description of sampling designs

According to CID 2013/652/EU, bovines under one year of age where the production of meat of those bovines in the Member State is more than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year must be sampled. However, as less than 10 000 tonnes bovines under one year of age are slaughtered in Austria, the AMR-monitoring is not mandatory and was performed.

E. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from bovines under one year at slaughterhouse

Description of sampling designs

According to CID 2013/652/EU, bovines under one year of age where the production of meat of those bovines in the Member State is more than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year must be sampled. However, as less than 10 000 tonnes bovines under one year of age are slaughtered in Austria, the AMR-monitoring is not mandatory and was performed.

F. Antimicrobial resistance of carbapenemase producing *E. coli* from bovines under one year at slaughterhouse

AMR Carbapenemase prod. *E. coli*

final

Description of sampling designs

According to CID 2013/652/EU, bovines under one year of age where the production of meat of those bovines in the Member State is more than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year must be sampled. However, as less than 10 000 tonnes bovines under one year of age are slaughtered in Austria, the AMR-monitoring is not mandatory and was performed.

5.1.3. Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolates from food

A. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from pork at retail

Description of sampling designs

The sampling plan is comprised from two different plans, one from the permanent routine sampling and the other from additional sampling, because the number of routine samples was too low.

Routine samples: This is the so-called advanced test-planning within the annual collection of routine samples by the Austrian Food Inspection on the basis of a report from the AGES sampling plan.

Approx. 150 samples are collected at retail all over Austria according to the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2015 acc. to article 31

Lebensmittelsicherheitsgesetz (LMSVG). This Revisions- und Probenplan is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004. Fresh pig meat is sampled by the food inspectors.

Additional samples: For those samples a separate plan for purchasing at retail was created. The purchase of fresh pig meat samples was carried out by AGES employees in Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Graz and Innsbruck. The sampling was stratified proportional to the population (including tourist nights) of the Austrian provinces in 2013 (source: Statistics Austria).

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Routine samples: AGES created a risk-based sampling plan to obtain the number of samples that had to be collected per food category, e.g. 150 fresh pork samples. 25% of samples were allocated to retail outlets in Vienna, the other samples distributed to the other provinces proportionally to their population (including tourist nights). Each province coordinated individually the sampling guaranteeing sample collections evenly distributed throughout the year.

Additional samples: The purchase of fresh pig meat samples at retail was carried out by AGES employees in Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Graz and Innsbruck. The sampling per AGES-site was distributed to all months of the year.

The total number of taken samples was checked on a quarterly basis and if necessary adapted to the next quarter.

All samples were collected as objective samples.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

The number of samples was allocated to each province proportionally based on their population including tourist nights. The retail outlets and meat batches were chosen randomly.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling was distributed evenly throughout the 12 months of the year.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Fresh pig meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Samples were placed in a sterile bag. The sample was transported in a refrigerator to one of the AGES Official Food Control Laboratories or one of the Regional Food Laboratories. From there the samples were forwarded to the NRL-AMR in Graz.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All samples were checked for conformity and invalid samples were excluded from analysis.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

In the laboratory all information was entered into the data base (LISA), also the lab results. The whole file with all data could be downloaded and analyzed using MS Excel ®.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocoll: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 1 and 2"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

According to CID 2013/652/EU; testings are performed in the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

According to CID 2013/652/EU.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 310 pig meat samples 224 samples were valid and could be analysed. In 22 samples suspected enzyme-producing *E. coli* were detected. In total, 19 ESBL-producing and one AmpC-producing *E. coli* were confirmed.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring was performed for the first time therefore no statement concerning trends over time can be made.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Molecular typing results will show which and how many of the isolated Enzyme-producing *E. coli* can also be found in human samples.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from beef at retail

Description of sampling designs

The sampling plan is comprised from two different plans, one from the permanent routine sampling and the other from additional sampling, because the number of routine samples was too low. Routine samples: This is the so-called advanced test-planning within the annual collection of routine samples by the Austrian Food Inspection on the basis of a report from the AGES sampling plan. Approx. 80 samples are collected at retail all over Austria according to the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2015 acc. to article 31 Lebensmittelsicherheitsgesetz (LMSVG). This Revisions- und Probenplan is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004. Fresh bovine meat is sampled by the food inspectors.

Additional samples: For those samples a separate plan for purchasing at retail was created. The purchase of fresh bovine meat samples was carried out by AGES employees in Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Graz and Innsbruck. The sampling was stratified proportional to the population (including tourist nights) of the Austrian provinces in 2013 (source: Statistics Austria).

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Routine samples: AGES created a risk-based sampling plan to obtain the number of samples that had to be collected per food category, e.g. 220 fresh bovine meat samples. 25% of samples were allocated to retail outlets in Vienna, the other samples distributed to the other provinces proportionally to their population (including tourist nights). Each province coordinated individually the sampling guaranteeing sample collections evenly distributed throughout the year.

Additional samples: The purchase of fresh bovine meat samples at retail was carried out by AGES employees in Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Graz and Innsbruck. The sampling per AGES-site was distributed to all months of the year.

The total number of taken samples was checked on a quarterly basis and if necessary adapted to the next quarter.

All samples were collected as objective samples.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

The number of samples was allocated to each province proportionally based on their population including tourist nights. The retail outlets and meat batches were chosen randomly.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling was distributed evenly throughout the 12 months of the year.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Fresh bovine meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Samples were placed in a sterile bag. The sample was transported in a refrigerator to one of the AGES Official Food Control Laboratories or one of the Regional Food Laboratories. From there the samples were forwarded to the NRL-AMR in Graz.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All samples were checked for conformity and invalid samples were excluded from analysis.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

In the laboratory all information was entered into the data base (LISA), also the lab results. The whole file with all data could be downloaded and analyzed using MS Excel[®].

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocol: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 1 and 2"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

According to CID 2013/652/EU; testings are performed in the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

According to CID 2013/652/EU.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 307 bovine meat samples 234 samples were valid and could be analyzed. In seven samples suspected enzyme-producing *E. coli* were detected, all seven were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring was performed for the first time therefore no statement concerning trends over time can be made.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Molecular typing results will show which and how many of the isolated Enzyme-producing *E. coli* can also be found in human samples.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

C. Antimicrobial resistance of carbapenemase producing *E. coli* from pork at retail

Description of sampling designs

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Notification system in place

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail pork fresh

Results of the investigation

216 samples of fresh pig meat were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

D. Antimicrobial resistance of carbapenemase producing *E. coli* from beef at retail

Description of sampling designs

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Notification system in place

See chapter ESBL/AmpC prod *E. coli* retail beef fresh

Results of the investigation

226 samples of fresh beef were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2015 (AURES 2015).

Table 79 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *E. coli* from food and animals, 2015

		ECOFF	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
antimicrobial		wild type <=	lowest	highest
panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,5	32
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,25	0,25	4
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0,5	0,5	8
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0,06	0,016	8
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,25	8
	macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64
	penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64
	polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	64	8	1024
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64
	trimethoprim	2	0,25	32
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0,06	0,016	2
	carbapenems - imipenem	0,5	0,12	16
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0,12	0,06	32
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,25	0,25	64
	cephalosporines - cefoxitin	8	0,5	64
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0,5	0,25	128
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	0,25	0,06	64
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	0,5	0,12	128
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0,5	128

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *E. coli* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 80 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in animals (qualitative tables), 2015

Panel 1	<i>E. coli</i>	pigs		
	antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
		N	%R	n
	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	163	2,5%	4
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	163	3,7%	6
	carbapenems - meropenem	163	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	163	2,5%	4
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	163	1,8%	3
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	163	4,9%	8
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	163	0,0%	0
	macrolides - azithromycin	163	0,0%	0
	penicillins - ampicillin	163	12,9%	21
	polymyxins - colistin	163	0,6%	1
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	163	3,1%	5
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	163	22,7%	37
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	163	47,2%	77
	trimethoprim	163	10,4%	17
	Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n
	fully sensitive	163	47,9%	78
	resistant to 1 antimicrobial	163	23,9%	39
	resistant to 2 antimicrobials	163	14,1%	23
	resistant to 3 antimicrobials	163	4,9%	8
	resistant to 4 antimicrobials	163	6,1%	10
	resistant to >4 antimicrobials	163	3,1%	5

Panel 2	antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
		N	%R	n
		carbapenems - ertapenem	4	0,0%
	carbapenems - imipenem	4	0,0%	0
	carbapenems - meropenem	4	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - cefepim	4	75,0%	3
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	4	75,0%	3
	cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	4	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	4	75,0%	3
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	4	0,0%	0
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	4	0,0%	0
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	4	0,0%	0

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 81 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in pigs - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	<i>E. coli</i>
matrix	pigs
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
	N	%R		n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	163	2,5%	4							137	19	3			1	1	1	1						
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	163	3,7%	6												154	3	3	1	2					
carbapenems - meropenem	163	0,0%	0		162	1																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	163	2,5%	4						159	1			1	2										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	163	1,8%	3						160	1	1	1												
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	163	4,9%	8		149	5	1	4	1			1			2									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	163	0,0%	0					94	68	1														
macrolides - azithromycin	163	0,0%	0								29	122	11	1										
penicillins - ampicillin	163	12,9%	21							9	70	56	7					21						
polymyxins - colistin	163	0,6%	1							159	3	1												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	163	3,1%	5									153	5					5						
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	163	22,7%	37										77	36	12	1							37	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	163	47,2%	77								75	11		1	2	26	48							
trimethoprim	163	10,4%	17					66	68	12							17							

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 81, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
						carbapenems - ertapenem	4	0,0%	0	0		3	1												
carbapenems - imipenem	4	0,0%	0	0					3		1														
carbapenems - meropenem	4	0,0%	0	0			4																		
cephalosporines - cefepim	4	75,0%	3	3				1			1					2									
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	4	75,0%	3	3						1			1				2								
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	4	0,0%	0	0									2		2										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	4	75,0%	3	3						1			3												
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	4	0,0%	0	0				4																	
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	4	0,0%	0	0					3	1															
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	4	0,0%	0	0										2	2										

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 82 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from animals and food (qualitative tables), 2015

ESBL		pigs			Pig meat			bovine meat		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
Panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	134	3,7%	5	19	10,5%	2	7	0,0%	0
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	134	8,2%	11	19	10,5%	2	7	42,9%	3
	carbapenems - meropenem	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	134	100,0%	134	19	100,0%	19	7	100,0%	7
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	134	87,3%	117	19	94,7%	18	7	85,7%	6
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	134	22,4%	30	19	21,1%	4	7	57,1%	4
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	macrolides - azithromycin	134	3,7%	5	19	5,3%	1	7	14,3%	1
	penicillins - ampicillin	134	100,0%	134	19	100,0%	19	7	100,0%	7
	polymyxins - colistin	134	0,7%	1	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	134	17,2%	23	19	15,8%	3	7	28,6%	2
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	134	47,8%	64	19	78,9%	15	7	57,1%	4
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	134	58,2%	78	19	52,6%	10	7	85,7%	6
	trimethoprim	134	45,5%	61	19	73,7%	14	7	42,9%	3
	Number of multiresistant isolates		N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R
fully sensitive		134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial		134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials		134	19,4%	26	19	10,5%	2	7	14,3%	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials		134	21,6%	29	19	15,8%	3	7	0,0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials		134	26,1%	35	19	31,6%	6	7	28,6%	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials		134	32,8%	44	19	42,1%	8	7	57,1%	4
Panel 2	antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
		N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
	carbapenems - ertapenem	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	carbapenems - imipenem	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	carbapenems - meropenem	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - cefepim	134	94,8%	127	19	100,0%	19	7	100,0%	7
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	134	100,0%	134	19	100,0%	19	7	100,0%	7
	cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	134	8,2%	11	19	5,3%	1	7	0,0%	0
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	134	89,6%	120	19	89,5%	17	7	85,7%	6
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	134	8,2%	11	19	5,3%	1	7	0,0%	0
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	134	8,2%	11	19	5,3%	1	7	0,0%	0	
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	134	0,0%	0	19	0,0%	0	7	0,0%	0	

Table 83, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
Panel 2	N	%R	n	n																			
carbapenems - ertapenem	134	0,0%	0	98	30	6																	
carbapenems - imipenem	134	0,0%	0				87	45	2														
carbapenems - meropenem	134	0,0%	0		132	2																	
cephalosporines - cefepim	134	94,8%	127			4	3		10	5	20	50	38	4									
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	134	100,0%	134							4	2	10	14	33	42	22	7						
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	134	8,2%	11								17	69	37	4	4	3							
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	134	89,6%	120					3	11	45	41	20	10	2	2								
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	134	8,2%	11			114	9		3	5		2	1										
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	134	8,2%	11				83	37	3	1	6	3		1									
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	134	0,0%	0								7	79	41	7									

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 84 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli from pork - at retail - quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	ESBL
matrix	pigs meat
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
	N	%R	n	n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	19	10,5%	2						14	1	2			1			1						
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	19	10,5%	2											16	1			2					
carbapenems - meropenem	19	0,0%	0		19																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	19	100,0%	19										4	15									
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	19	94,7%	18						1	8	2	3	4	1									
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	19	21,1%	4	15				1					1	2									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	19	0,0%	0					14	5														
macrolides - azithromycin	19	5,3%	1								1	15	2				1						
penicillins - ampicillin	19	100,0%	19															19					
polymyxins - colistin	19	0,0%	0							19													
quinolones - nalidixic acid	19	15,8%	3										15	1					3				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	19	78,9%	15											4								15	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	19	52,6%	10								8		1				6	4					
trimethoprim	19	73,7%	14					4	1								14						

Table 84, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
	N	%R	n	n																			
carbapenems - ertapenem	19	0,0%	0	18	1																		
carbapenems - imipenem	19	0,0%	0				14	4	1														
carbapenems - meropenem	19	0,0%	0	19																			
cephalosporines - cefepim	19	100,0%	19					2		5	4	7	1										
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	19	100,0%	19									6	1	9	2	1							
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	19	5,3%	1								1	13	4			1							
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	19	89,5%	17						2	2	8	2	3	2									
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	19	5,3%	1			18								1									
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	19	5,3%	1				13	5						1									
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	19	0,0%	0								3	10	6										

Table 85 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli from beef - at retail - quantitative data, 2015

zoonotic agent	ESBL
matrix	bovine meat
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
			n																					
	N	%R	n																					
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0,0%	5 2																					
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	42,9%	4 1 2																					
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0,0%	7																					
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	100,0%	2 2 3																					
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	85,7%	1 2 2 2																					
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	57,1%	2 1 2 2																					
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	7	0,0%	6 1																					
macrolides - azithromycin	7	14,3%	3 3 1																					
penicillins - ampicillin	7	100,0%	7																					
polymyxins - colistin	7	0,0%	7																					
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	28,6%	2 3 2																					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	57,1%	3 4																					
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	85,7%	1 3 3																					
trimethoprim	7	42,9%	3 1 3																					

Table 85, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
Panel 2	N	%R	n	n																			
carbapenems - ertapenem	7	0,0%	0	6	1																		
carbapenems - imipenem	7	0,0%	0				4	3															
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0,0%	0		7																		
cephalosporines - cefepim	7	100,0%	7					2	1	1		2	1										
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	100,0%	7								2	2		1	1	1							
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	7	0,0%	0								1	4	2										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	85,7%	6						1		3	1		2									
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	7	0,0%	0			7																	
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	7	0,0%	0				5	2															
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	7	0,0%	0								1	3	3										

5.2. *Enterococcus* Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria from 2004 to 2012 but that program was suspended in 2013.

6. Food-borne outbreaks

Food-borne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a food-borne outbreak.

A. Food-borne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food-borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food-borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (62 of 78) of food-borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - could decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2015, 78 food-borne outbreaks affecting 333 persons were reported. 86 persons were hospitalized and no lethal cases. The total number of food-borne outbreaks decreased by 19 % compared to 2014. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 4.3 persons, ranging from two to 141 persons per outbreak. 18 % (13.5 % in 2014, 16 % in 2013, 14 % in 2012) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 44 % of all food-borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=28), 41 % by *Salmonella* (n=26) and 69 % thereof by serovar Enteritidis (n=18) compared to (57 %) in 2014.

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 85 % of all food borne outbreaks (91 % in 2014, 77 % in 2013, 93 % in 2012). Presently, the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

25.8 (15.3 % in 2014; 19 % in 2013; 17.3 % in 2012) of patients affected by these food-borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized; no one died in association with an outbreak.

Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

Annual Report of the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* for the year 2015, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, Graz, Austria; 2016. Available from:

<http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/3/1/2/CH1075/CMS1457967544485/salmonellenjahresbericht2015.pdf>

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Food Safety Authority. Multi-country outbreak of *Salmonella* Stanley infections –Third update, 8 May 2014. Stockholm and Parma: ECDC/EFSA; 2014. Available from:

http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/scientific_output/files/main_documents/592e.pdf

Springer B, Allerberger F, Kornschöber C (2014) Letter to the editor: *Salmonella* Stanley outbreaks – a prompt to reevaluate existing food regulations. Euro Surveill 19(22):pii=20818. Available from:

<http://www.eurosurveillance.org/images/dynamic/EE/V19N22/art20818.pdf>

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Additional information

The situation of foodborne outbreaks are published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 86 Food-borne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2015

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food	Contributory Factors
3767	C. botulinum toxin	1	2	2	0	Canned food products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	Household	Household	Household	AT	Cross-contamination
3598	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Bovine meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household	Household	Household	XX	Other contributory factor
3682	Flavivirus - Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBE)	1	2	2	0	Milk	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household	Farm	Farm	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
3820	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	0	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
33	Salmonella - S. Stanley	1	141	45	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Take-away or fast-food outlet	Processing plant	EU	Cross-contamination, unprocessed contaminated ingredient
3710	Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin A	1	5	2	0	Sweets and chocolate	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown

Data source: EMS as of May 13, 2016

Table 87 Food-borne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2015

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks		Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
		Number of Cases	Number of								
3612	C. botulinum toxin	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3601	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	AT	Unknown
3701	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3891	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	9	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Canteen or workplace catering	XX	Infected food handler
3932	Campylobacter - C. coli	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3665	Campylobacter - C. coli	1	3	2	0	Sweets and chocolate	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3560	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3671	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3732	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3733	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3768	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3779	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3842	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3847	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3882	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3883	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	5	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3885	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3584	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3756	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3784	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	4	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3787	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3863	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	
3888	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
3530	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household	Household	XX	Inadequate heat treatment

Table 87 continued

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks		Number of Cases		Number of Deaths		Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
		1	2	0	0	0	0							
3660	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0			Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household	Take-away or fast-food outlet	Mobile retailer or market/street vendor	XX	Unknown
3714	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0			Pig meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Inadequate heat treatment
3608	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	1	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3617	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	
3672	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3773	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3783	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	3	1	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household		XX	
3880	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3899	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household		XX	Unknown
3737	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	4	1	0			Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3912	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	8	2	0			Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	General	Temporary mass catering (fairs or festivals)	Temporary mass catering (fairs or festivals)	XX	Unknown
3603	Salmonella - S. 1,4,12:i:-	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3837	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 13a	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3708	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	2	1	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3844	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 2	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3528	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3789	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 29	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3645	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3654	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3753	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3758	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	1	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3760	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0			Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Table 87 continued

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
3763	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	5	2	0	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3769	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3785	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3790	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	2	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3802	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3867	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3915	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	2	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3786	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3793	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	2	0	Bovine meat and products thereof	Household	Household	Household	AT	Unknown
3829	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Household	Household	Household	XX	Inadequate heat treatment
3576	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	2	0	Eggs and egg products	General	Household	Household	XX	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
3821	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 9a	1	2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3723	Salmonella - S. Haifa	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Household	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3761	Salmonella - S. Kambole	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3788	Salmonella - S. Mikawasima	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown		XX	
3864	Salmonella - S. Stanley	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3804	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 1	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3897	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 1	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Others	XX	Unknown
3571	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 39	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3817	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - RDNC	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3638	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Household	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3917	Shigella - S. sonnei	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3566	Shigella - S. sonnei	1	2	0	0	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3755	Shigella - S. sonnei	1	2	0	0	Unknown	General	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3825	Shigella - S. sonnei	1	2	0	0	Unknown	General	Unknown		XX	Unknown
3822	Shigella - Shigella spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0	Cheese	Household	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Data source: EMS as of May 13, 2016

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Staphylococcal food intoxication is not a major health problem in Austria. Nevertheless there are two staphylococcal food poisoning outbreaks documented in the last 10 years.

September 2006: Outbreak of an acute gastroenteritis in an Austrian boarding school caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* producing Enterotoxins A and D in rice. Afflicted were 113 persons/101 hospitalised because of vomiting and circulatory collapse. The rice had been contaminated by a kitchenstaff.

June 2007: Outbreak of staphylococcal food intoxication after consumption of pasteurized milk products. 166 children had fallen ill with abdominal cramps and vomiting caused by school milk products containing staphylococcal Enterotoxins A and D. The source of the contamination was three milk producing cows with subclinical mastitis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The analysis of food samples consists of two steps, a prescreening to identify samples harbouring > 100,000 coagulase-positive staphylococci CFU per gram; in that case, a second screening step is applied directly in all types of food matrices according to the European screening method given by the EURL for coagulase positive staphylococci to detect staphylococcal enterotoxins (SE) types A to E. The direct testing for staphylococcal enterotoxins is done in case of outbreaks or when food was pasteurised or heated before the screening for coagulasepositive staphylococci.

Because it is not known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Hygiene is of utmost importance in food producing process and in the kitchen to prevent contamination with coagulasepositive staphylococci. Additionally precautions must be taken to ensure and control the effective maintaining of the refrigeration chain.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started to improve harmonization of the detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins types A to E in food matrices.

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2015, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan fuer das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien ueber die Vollziehung der Ueberwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2015“ (BMG-75500/0176-II/B/13/2014) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2015, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2015, 6 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Definition of positive finding

Detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E in food .

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Prescreening: Several food (e. g. icecream, meat, cheese, etc.) is tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. If the number of detected staphylococci exceeds 100,000 CFU/g, the food matrices are further tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E following the “European screening method of the EU-RL for coagulasepositive staphylococci, including *Staphylococcus aureus*” using commercially available ELISAs. A positive screening result leads to an identification of the toxin group by another ELISA or a RPLA (Reverse passive latex agglutination).

Positive isolates are sent to the National Reference Laboratory in Graz, where the Enterotoxins A, B, C1, C2, C3, D, E are identified via an ELFA (enzyme linked fluorescent assay). RPLA and ELISAs for further investigations on the enterotoxins may complete the analysis.

Results of the investigation

Because it is not exactly known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

7.2. Cronobacter sakazakii

7.2.1. Cronobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Infant formula

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 88 Cronobacter sakazakii in food, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Cronobacter sakazakii
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
Infant formula		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Fish, fishery products, cheese

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400 mg histamine per kg cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-026-15: Histamine in food – fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – single (food/feed) – at catering – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January to April

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured (tuna samples in open cans from restaurants and food stalls)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 10 g

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg/kg for fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

Results of the investigation

94 samples were tested for Histamine: Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured: total units in non-conformity: 6 (>400 mg/kg)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. This food campaign was already done in 2013 (A-024-13), positive samples increased from 19 % to 23.4 % in 2015. For the year 2017, further investigations are suggested.

Table 89 Histamine in food, 2015

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units in non-conformity	<=100 mg/kg	>100 to <=200 mg/kg	>200 to <=400 mg/kg	>400 mg/kg	
Crustaceans		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	batch (food/feed)			10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	A-026-15	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	1	0	0	0	0	1
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	64	5	0	0	0	0	5
XX			single (food/feed)	10	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	EU	batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	
		XE	batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	
Fishery products, unspecified	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - raw - chilled	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	

8. Index of Tables

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of animals, herds, holdings and slaughtered animals, 2015 - 14 -	
Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015.....	- 20 -
Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015	- 22 -
Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2015	- 22 -
Table 5 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2015	- 27 -
Table 6 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2015.....	- 29 -
Table 7 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in milk and dairy products, 2015	- 33 -
Table 8 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in other food, 2015	- 35 -
Table 9 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in poultry breeding flocks (<i>Gallus gallus</i>), 2015	- 54 -
Table 10 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in other commercial poultry, 2015	- 55 -
Table 11 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2015.....	- 59 -
Table 12 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2015	- 60 -
Table 13 <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in other feed matter, 2015	- 61 -
Table 14 <i>Salmonella</i> serovars in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015	- 62 -
Table 15 <i>S. Enteritidis</i> phage types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015.....	- 65 -
Table 16 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015	- 66 -
Table 17 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic, definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2015.....	- 67 -
Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of <i>Salmonella</i> spp., 2015.....	- 70 -
Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 71 -
Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Enteritidis</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 72 -
Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Typhimurium</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 73 -
Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Typhimurium</i> monophasic strain in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 74 -
Table 23 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Stanley</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 75 -
Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Infantis</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 76 -
Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Agona</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 77 -
Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Montevideo</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 78 -
Table 27 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Mbandaka</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 79 -
Table 28 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Saintpaul</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 80 -
Table 29 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>S. Senftenberg</i> in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 81 -
Table 30 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before in humans, poultry meat and poultry flocks (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2015	- 82 -
Table 31 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015	- 85 -
Table 32 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015	- 85 -
Table 33 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2015	- 85 -
Table 34 Thermotolerant <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in poultry meat, 2015	- 89 -
Table 35 Thermotolerant <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in food, 2015.....	- 90 -

Table 36 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> and <i>C. coli</i> , 2015 . - 94 -	
Table 37 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> , qualitative data, 2015	- 95 -
Table 38 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> in humans, quantitative data, 2015 - 96 -	
Table 39 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> in broiler meat, fresh, quantitative data, 2015.....	- 97 -
Table 40 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> in Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation, quantitative data, 2015	- 98 -
Table 41 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> in Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - offal, quantitative data, 2015	- 99 -
Table 42 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> in turkey meat, fresh, quantitative data, 2015.....	- 100 -
Table 43 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> , qualitative data, 2015.....	- 101 -
Table 44 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in humans, quantitative data, 2015 - 102 -	
Table 45 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in broiler meat, fresh - quantitative data, 2015.....	- 103 -
Table 46 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - quantitative data, 2015	- 104 -
Table 47 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - offal - quantitative data, 2015	- 105 -
Table 48 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in turkey meat, fresh - quantitative data, 2015.....	- 106 -
Table 49 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i> in Meat from turkey - meat preparation - quantitative data, 2015	- 107 -
Table 50 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015	- 110 -
Table 51 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-L), 2015	- 110 -
Table 52 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2015	- 111 -
Table 53 <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in milk and milky products, 2015	- 115 -
Table 54 <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in other foods, 2015.....	- 118 -
Table 55 Verocytotoxic <i>Escherichia coli</i> infections in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2015.....	- 126 -
Table 56 Verocytotoxic <i>Escherichia coli</i> infections in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2015 - 126 -	
Table 57 Verocytotoxic <i>Escherichia coli</i> in food, 2015.....	- 130 -
Table 58 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-Tbc), 2015.....	- 141 -
Table 59 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution (NRC-Tbc), 2015	- 142 -
Table 60 Bovine tuberculosis in 2015	- 146 -
Table 61 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2015.....	- 147 -
Table 62 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2015.....	- 149 -
Table 63 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2015	- 150 -
Table 64 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing (non co-financed), 2015.....	- 156 -
Table 65 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2015	- 157 -
Table 66 Yersiniosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2015	- 159 -
Table 67 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2015.....	- 160 -
Table 68 <i>Yersinia</i> spp. in food, 2015	- 161 -
Table 69 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015	- 163 -
Table 70 <i>Trichinella</i> spp. in animals, 2015	- 167 -
Table 71 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015	- 169 -
Table 72 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2015.....	- 170 -
Table 73 <i>Echinococcus</i> sp. in animals, 2015.....	- 171 -
Table 74 Toxoplasmosis cases in pregnant and fetus (NRL-T), 2015	- 173 -

Table 75 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2015	- 174 -
Table 76 Rabies in humans, 2015	- 176 -
Table 77 Rabies in animals, 2015	- 178 -
Table 78 Q-fever in animals, 2015	- 180 -
Table 79 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of <i>E. coli</i> from food and animals, 2015	- 193 -
Table 80 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>E. coli</i> in animals (qualitative tables), 2015	- 194 -
Table 81 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>E. coli</i> in pigs - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2015	- 195 -
Table 82 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of ESBL/AmpC producing <i>E. coli</i> from animals and food (qualitative tables), 2015	- 197 -
Table 83 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>E. coli</i> in pigs - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2015	- 198 -
Table 84 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>E. coli</i> from pork - at retail - quantitative data, 2015	- 200 -
Table 85 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>E. coli</i> from beef - at retail - quantitative data, 2015.....	- 202 -
Table 86 Food-borne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2015	- 207 -
Table 87 Food-borne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2015	- 208 -
Table 88 <i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i> in food, 2015	- 213 -
Table 89 Histamine in food, 2015	- 216 -

